

TOWARDS
A NATIONAL
COLLECTION

Arts and
Humanities
Research Council

FINAL REPORT

DISCOVERY PROJECTS

Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections- Based Industrial Histories

Science Museum Group | University of Leeds
University of London | Historic England
University College London | University of Liverpool
British Film Institute

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Table of Contents

1. Executive Summary	1
2. Abstract	5
3. Aims, Objectives and Delivery.....	6
4. Partnership Structure	11
5. Staffing Structure	14
6. Overall Programme	17
7. Events and Presentations	19
8. Research Approach.....	29
9. Research Results	34
10. Project Outputs	43
11. Cross-Project Collaboration	49
12. Infrastructure, Data Management and Sustainability	50
13. Final Recommendations	54
14. Contacts	59
15. Annex: List of Investigations	60
16. Works Cited.....	81

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1. Executive Summary

Congruence Engine has addressed its stated aims and objectives. We set out to be a true research project: exploratory and experimental, and the evidence of this can be seen throughout this report and especially in the research results section (9), which lays out our argument, and in our 40+ investigations listed in the annex. The path taken wasn't precisely the one proposed at application-writing stage, but the core intentions and spirit have been more than fulfilled. We opted for a systemic action research approach to enable the project's effort to flex with research needs. In the end, the project passed through four 'eras' (see section 6: Overall programme and 8: Research Approach).

The reasoning behind the project and its conclusions are laid out in section 9: Research Results. The abstract is reproduced here:

"We want to make all UK heritage collections fully accessible together, not just institution-by institution as now, to those who would use them. The means to achieve this are their digital records. But, because of the history of heritage organisations, our current records are ill-suited for this purpose: in the main, they are thin, inconsistent and isolate collections items from the contexts in which they make sense. In *Congruence Engine*, we have therefore experimentally created ways to link collections with historical data as well as with each other, techniques that in various ways overcome these weaknesses. Because the creation of useful collections linkage requires the agency of its potential users, and because computing techniques are fallible, UK collections linkage requires a social machine for the task: a human-technical approach that mobilises human motivation and thereby overcomes machine incapacities. Many of our techniques employ machine learning, with the result that we have within our grasp the capacity to overcome decades of limited investment in collection documentation. But, because we are using these techniques, we confront a series of ethical issues that demand to be researched, even as we press for the resources to create user interfaces and scalable prototypes for a future infrastructure, which together can reveal the potential of what we have glimpsed."

The outcome of our body of investigations (described in the annex) supports our recommendations (section 13) that centre on the creation, not of a 'national collection' (as we first termed our aspiration), but of 'UK collections linkage'. This, we propose, should be achieved by datafication of collections catalogues and via linked open data (LOD) techniques. This will entail heritage organisations expanding data held in digital form about collections items so as to enhance especially: data on the associations and purposes of objects (and other collections items), and tightening of dating. Contextual associations, including from exhibition texts, catalogues, publications and support files should also be converted into data to maximise institutional retention of narrative understanding, and thereby linkage to other collections and greatly increased research use of all kinds. Techniques including Named Entity Recognition deployed on such expanded collections data can enable linkage to associated items and histories across collections, especially by use of Wikidata (or functionally similar services).

Sample possibilities arising from *Congruence Engine* research:

- Visual search across collections (investigation 5) to enable identification of objects and of areas of strength and weakness across the nation's holdings.
- Linking similar objects across collections via terminology extraction (9) and Wikidata (10) to pool understanding and interpretation across the sector, to enable greater use and – potentially – to

reduce duplication. Also using the same techniques to work thematically across collections of differing kinds, enabling contextual histories and creative curation.

- Using digitisation then datafication using Resource Augmented Retrieval (RAG) to associate object interpretation (catalogues, display texts, file material) with collections items to aid discoverability and use (15).
- Automatically linking museum object records to contemporary texts (14) and historical interpretation (5) as an alternative to extensive expert re-cataloguing, and to enable significant increase in historical use of collections.
- Creation of ontologies (digital models linking people, machines, places, products, materials and products) to enable large-scale historical work incorporating heritage items into historical and curatorial accounts (23).
- Using generative AI technologies to produce good basic formatted catalogue descriptions from available data (8, 16).
- Using geospatial association to link collections items of different kinds by place of manufacture, association, or depiction (17, 18).

Heritage organisations stand to gain from these kinds of activity as they will serve the core public purpose of making whole collections – not just the small minority on display – visible to the people who would use them, and justify the retention of large collections by realising our promise that they are held for public use. This is especially true for the substantial number of heritage organisations that have recently centralised their offsite storage.

The creation of UK collections linkage requires four categories of funded activity in overlapping phases (Recommendations, section 8):

- Continuing research: to create the needed scalable prototypes for a future infrastructure (large scale proof-of-concept, building on TaNC), the (digital) apps and user interfaces, and debate on the (ethical) frameworks to enable this. This may best continue on a project basis.
- Digitisation and datafication of collections to enable their linkage (rolling-out the necessary transformations and techniques across the GLAM sector). This should be enacted on a programme – not project – basis at the decade-length scale.
- Creation and readily availability of social historical datasets for linkage.
- Long-term implementation of linkage by a wide variety of organisations and people supported by techniques and frameworks developed in i, acting on data produced in ii and iii.

Technical underpinnings for collections linkage in terms of infrastructure, data management and sustainability are detailed in section 12. A key project principle was that our infrastructure choices and decisions should be pragmatic, using existing digital tools rather than building bespoke solutions, and particularly having in mind the sustainability of systems and outputs. In *Congruence Engine*, each investigation team was able to customise their own working and development environment by choosing from existing digital services and tools. We propose that this kind of approach can and should be pursued to deliver collections linkage more broadly. A minimal infrastructure for a linked collection would include a simple data register (to record the whereabouts of data representing collections and record linkages) of the kind we have trialled (investigation 24). This could, with benefit, be accompanied by a resource index (listing ontologies, thesauruses, gazetteers, etc). Together, these could support people (heritage organisation staff,

university academics and interested lay people) in the work of linking heritage collection items to each other and to other data sources.

If *Congruence Engine* itself has been a social machine, whose human members have brought a diversity of expertise, life experience, capability, and energy, we also recommend this model for the conduct of the next stages of the work. The metaphor is apposite: the work ahead requires the power of automation enabled by new Large Language Model technologies. But it intrinsically also needs the care, contribution and connections enabled by participants of all kinds: employees of heritage organisations, researchers in the universities and a diverse array of community groups and individuals with interests in history and heritage. For linkage of collections to have purpose, it must be of a kind that serves the interests and needs of people of all kinds.

Race and Decolonisation

Our steering group helped us to make a decisive move to address issues of coloniality and racism in relation to the collections our organisations hold, and those to which we would want to link. No one who took part in our race and decolonisation group (see section 8, research approach) thinks about these issues the same way as they did before the project. There is work to do, not only in addressing archaic data and absences in collections, and in gaining a deeper understanding of the origins of our collections in an extractive imperial age, but also in developing approaches to equity in the forthcoming work on collections linkage that recognise the structural inequalities of our sector and in what it represents via its collections and public works.

Skills

We shared with other Discovery Projects the core initial difficulty of recruiting data scientists. Here we have some grounds for optimism that the TaNC programme itself may have begun to make in-roads in what seemed in 2022 to be an insuperable difficulty: there existed no model career path for heritage data science. At that point this felt like a defining issue of humanities-heritage-computational interdisciplinary work. We also feared at the start that there were major differences in the work culture expectations of these three sectors: that good humanities research is comfortable with open-endedness; heritage workers mainly do practical problem-solving, and computing professionals manage risk within a contract-framed model of delivery. In the end, and especially through the project's 'second era' of intensive digital investigations, we found that collaborative working across disciplines, and researchers' appetite for working in a hybrid fashion created models of practice, and individuals, who will be able to take this work forward.

Outputs

It has been a fundamental assumption that our work should be widely accessible (see sections 7 and 10). We published a [special issue](#) of the (open access, online) *Science Museum Group Journal* after a year. We aim to publish two open access books in early 2026: the 18-chapter *Emergent Histories: New Work in the Digital History of Industry and Collections from the Congruence Engine Project* (UCL Press) and *The UK Digital Collection: A Manifesto* (University of London Press). Other papers are appearing in specialist journals. [Our blog](#), with its 22 posts, has provided a window on the project's key concepts and developments. Team members spoke at digital humanities and history of science conferences and took part in TaNC webinars and

in the programme's final Manchester conference. Our project's own final conference, joint with the annual Artefacts Consortium conference (of researchers associated with science museums worldwide), put the project's achievements before a deeply interested core global audience. We have established a GitHub repository for data and code and will devote a section of the Science Museum Group British Library-hosted data repository to key documents and outputs from the project. We produced two exhibits: the first, at the Discovery Museum in Newcastle, aimed to show the ambitions of the project via four short films. The second, a fully interactive digital exhibit which will run at the Science and Media Museum in Bradford from early 2025, makes accessible a huge number of heritage items within a map-based interactive that also reveals some of the digital tools we have used. In addition to the four exhibit films, Common Films have produced *Bradford Forwards and Backwards*, a 25-minute film inspired by the project, showcasing links between Bradford mills and textiles work in this post-industrial city.

2. Abstract

The capacity to make strong connections between historical objects and sources lies at the heart of this project as it does in the everyday museum and historical practices that it is designed to support. Curators creating displays combine artefacts, images, audio-visual materials and histories often drawn from several heritage organisations. Family and local historians connect records from a diversity of sources that illuminate ancestors and localities so as to establish their genealogy or to understand the past of where they live. Academic historians patiently and critically connect a diverse range of archive sources with existing literature to tell new stories about the past. All rely on connecting different fragments of the past as they sew the quilts of narrative that constitute our local, national and international histories. The difference with this *Towards a National Collection* project is that it seeks to make such linkages at the national scale (and beyond) of all collections, enabling access together to significant numbers of relevant items from across many GLAM organisations holding heritage in many media. In place of the two-dimensional ranked list of search engines, with *Congruence Engine*, we have modelled a world in which users will be able to explore data neighbourhoods where a great diversity of information about heritage items from many sources that are deeply relevant to their investigations will be readily to hand – museum objects, archive documents, pictures, films, buildings, and the records of previous investigations and relevant activity.

3. Aims, Objectives and Delivery

As we describe in more detail elsewhere (section 8), our project has passed through four ‘eras’ post-startup: In 2023, a period of small-scale investigations establishing the possibilities of associating collections; in 2022-4, a multi-strand period of intensive parallel investigations; and in 2024, a period of public engagement followed by another of the concentrated production of project outputs. Below we quote the original application’s aims and objectives (selectively modified in light of project experience), adding a commentary on the research and what it has taught us.

- 1. Our stated project aim was: ‘Via an action research methodology to use real-world historical enquiries of community-, museum- and university-based historians and curators to hone digital tools needed for proof of concept of a linked national collection, using the example of industrial history.’**

The action research methodology has been a core resource for the conduct of the project from the outset, setting the tone of the enquiry from the opening conference in February 2022 onwards. In the course of the first year, we combined our Project Management and Action Research work packages to the significant benefit of the project. In the funding application, we explained how the action research approach would enable project members to respond to the emergence of unforeseen research opportunities. As we anticipated, it has been valuable at the micro- and the macro- scale, enabling the project to flex the investigation in response to the pressures and opportunities emergent from the research. In particular, it enabled our ‘digital turn’ into our second era in late 2022, which coincided with the launch of ChatGPT, ushering-in an unanticipated range of technical possibilities.

In terms of participation, we were fortunate to have amongst our partner organisations the Saltaire World Heritage Education Association / Saltaire History Club and the Local Authority technology museums Discovery Museum in Newcastle and Bradford Industrial Museum. These partnerships enabled us to experiment with participation despite the finding, from early in the project, that enrolling participants is by no means easy. In part, we reflected, this was because our core proposition – that there are benefits to historical practice in digitally linking collections – may be obvious to museum curators, but it proved to be more difficult to convey it to professional and amateur historians. It was necessary, from within the resources of the project, to produce examples of these benefits. But we determined to devote investigatory firepower to understanding what participation on the ground would mean. This was enacted first via an evaluation undertaken with local history enthusiasts of project ideas in the context of our Newcastle exhibit in February 2024. We took this to the next stage in our parallel and significantly longer ‘Bradford convergence’, where months of discussions with Bradford community groups eventuated in a series of organised participatory events. All of our participatory work has been about understanding the means by which different people and groups can define the terms of their involvement (and the overall governance implications of a federated system). In so doing, we have sought to avoid tokenistic and extractive inclusion practice.

We can be confident in the relevance to historical practice, as is testified by the chapters in the project’s first book, *Emergent Histories: New Work in the Digital History of Industry and Collections from the Congruence Engine Project*, to be published by UCL Press in early 2026. Research Fellows and investigators brought their historical imaginations and experience to their individual investigations and so, whether it be histories of river pollution, of curatorial practice or family histories in Bradford – to name just a few – new historical work has emerged.

2. To conduct three industrial sector-based investigations using heterogeneous collections. Textiles, energy and communications are here used to map the changing history of industry, society and culture over 250 years.

The project taught us that the sketched sequential approach giving nine months' attention to each of the three industrial sectors was not appropriate and so we pursued them in a layered manner (see section 8). This was partially because it took a cycle of action research to demonstrate that it would be necessary to find a way, despite recruitment difficulties, to make the project more digital, employing more digital tools and using large datasets. We worked pragmatically to develop the investigations even while we awaited the full availability of our more technical appointees. It also became clear that the cycles of research activity would mostly need to be longer than the three months initially envisaged. As the Large Language Model technologies came on stream from late 2022, the affordances of differing kinds of LLM technology came to dominate somewhat (and valuably), but used on subjects drawn from across our themes.

3. To represent museum culture and STEM history within the set of Discovery Projects.

The TaNC funding schemes' core concern with 'break[ing] down the barriers that exist between the UK's outstanding cultural heritage collections' has been central to everything we have done.¹ As an IRO-led project, Congruence Engine was motivated by a strong felt need for museum collections to be better known and significantly better used, including in research.

The differences between museum 'museum as method' styles of research and those of the Academy rose up the project's agenda in the first 18 months,² because kinds of practice that draw on many collections and on differing media are typical of museum work (especially in display), but less so in the universities.

Histories of science, technology, engineering and medicine represented in our consortium also occur in at least one other Discovery Project, but in *Congruence Engine* they are the core concern. Furthermore, the collections we can link are products of the collecting histories of institutions. In the case of technical museums, understanding how our curatorial ancestors conceptualised the history of technology is key to unlocking understanding of the collections that exist, the data that represent them, and the relative ease of linking them to undertake work in social history, for example (this is the subject of two chapters in our *Emergent Histories* book).

As we have worked to synthesize our findings from the project, another sense of the salience of history of science / Science and Technology Studies has emerged: we have become acutely aware of the experience of living through a technological revolution – the kind of subject that we might otherwise be studying, including an awareness of factors such as technological unemployment.³

4. To pursue kinds of interdisciplinary and intermedial research that are specifically enabled by the uniting of heterogeneous kinds of heritage items and their data.

The research is necessarily interdisciplinary, even at the level of combining humanities with digital expertise; the action research adds a third kind of practice to the mix, whilst recognising that museum modes of research (see 3 above) differ from those of universities adds a fourth. We are committed to making the research inter-not just multi-disciplinary. The project consortium was planned with the aim of enabling intermedial studies. It is true that the project has brought together museum objects with library and archive sources, including maps. Films have been brought into contact with oral testimony, and photographs with historic building records. The

potential for denser and bigger intermedial working has been sketched – perhaps most clearly in our public-facing final exhibit – but its fuller exploration must await new projects, and the affordances of the UK collections linkage we advocate.

5. To conduct the investigation UK-wide: Bradford, Manchester, Newcastle, London, Edinburgh, etc.

In addition to the sites of planned activity, we had Project Partners from across the UK, including National Museums Northern Ireland and National Museums Scotland. There are two aspects to what we achieved here. First, we should concede that the pragmatics of the project meant less geographical diversity of activity than we'd originally hoped for. That proofs-of-concept of collections linkage were required before community groups could be enrolled pushed such participation later in the project, to Newcastle in February 2024 and, overlappingly to Bradford across the first seven months of 2024. Pragmatism drove the return to the latter city: prior experience with community groups, our bank of wool industry textile investigations, and the coincident announcement of Bradford as City of Culture for 2025 all pointed in this direction. Second, especially in the project's geospatial mapping work, we demonstrated the power of linking data relating to historic industrial activity and its related collections, not just across the UK, but internationally.

The techniques we have developed are ripe for roll-out more widely across the UK and beyond. What we have demonstrated in the case of Bradford – the power of linked data incorporating all kinds of heritage collections – could be applied in any town or region, to the benefit of citizens and heritage collections everywhere.

6. To create appropriate outputs for all audiences: general and enthusiast public and scholars.

Interested individuals have been able to read the project blog (19 issues, starting from February 2022, with the potential for some final summative contributions before project end). The special issue of the [Science Museum Group Journal](#) is available open access to anyone. We created a film-based exhibit that ran at the Discovery Museum Newcastle from October 2023 to February 2024 (the films can be seen [here](#)). Our final, fully interactive, exhibit will open in Bradford in early January 2025 and remain on show for at least half of Bradford's City of Culture year. Bradford Forwards and Backwards, a 25-minute film inspired by the project, will show at selected film festivals in 2025 before being made generally available via the Science Museum's British Library-hosted Research Repository.

Team members delivered papers at relevant conferences across the three years, notably to audiences in digital humanities and history of science, culminating in the joint end of project-Artefacts consortium 2.5 day international conference at the Science Museum in October 2024 and the TaNC conference in Manchester in November 2024.

Two books are in preparation, for publication early in 2026: *Emergent Histories: New Work in the Digital History of Industry and Collections* from the *Congruence Engine* Project, to be published by UCL Press, and the novella-length *The UK Digital Collection: A Manifesto*, which is with University of London Press. Further articles are appearing in appropriate specialist journals, including, potentially within a Science Museum Group Journal Artefacts conference-derived special issue.

7. To create, enable and sustain a multidisciplinary team with appropriate skills to deliver the project aims.

The Action Research methodology worked well to convene the team and to set their priorities. As the project commenced during the pandemic, it carried some of that period's working assumptions into the remainder of its

delivery. The staff were distributed across the country and mainly worked hybrid, enabled by online meetings and semi-regular attendance at the Science Museum research centre, especially for the core fortnightly Investigations meeting. A most effective alternating fortnightly 'Drop-In' session led by University of London data scientist Kunika Kono provided mentoring and training for team members in digital techniques, and this was complemented by two rounds of formal training.

8. To enhance the cross-disciplinary skills of participants, especially the employability of early career researchers (ECRs).

The Research Fellows (mainly early career) and indeed the whole team worked across disciplines, learning digital, curatorial, historical and participative skills. All team members were encouraged to draw on each other's wide and deep experience, and this was mobilised in all the writing projects, where co-writing has been the norm.

The early career researchers particularly have gained valuable interdisciplinary skillsets. Virtually all the Discovery Projects, especially at the start, found it difficult to recruit data scientists, but our researchers have gained a valuable set of skills mixing humanities and curatorial instincts with humanities and digital capability. Those from backgrounds in the history of science and technology have become proficient in using digital tools, and our data scientists have gained insights into working to humanities research principles. Both groups deserve to find employment in what should be a burgeoning field of heritage data practice and indeed, two already have.

9. To test the application of a range of digital techniques and technologies, including a range of Machine Learning/AI methods, in identifying and modelling potential linkage between heterogenous datasets, of varying analogue/digital/machine-readable/semantically modelled status. To reflect critically on consequent issues including biases in existing collections, processes of digitisation, the digitalisation of existing method, and the emergence of new AI techniques, and ethical considerations in relation to these.

The project has trialled, through its investigations, a huge variety of digital technologies, many more than we could have expected, given the generative AI boom. Project researchers have used:

- Optical Character Recognition (OCR) models to: extract information from historic sources in a variety of formats
- Speech to text converters, including Whisper, to transcribe oral histories and the commentary tracks of documentary films; to transcribe researcher interviews.
- Surprising Phrase Detection: to explore archaic catalogue terminology.
- Named Entity Recognition models to: identify key terms and construct specialist vocabularies.
- Large Language Models (LLMs), including Chat GPT, to: parse OCR'd directories; create a chatbot to answer questions about textile machinery; to write Python and other code; to write archive catalogue entries; and to generate embeddings for semantic search databases, for example.
- ChatGPT to create a chatbot focussed on communications history in Bradford, and then OpenAI's GPT model to create a Retrieval Augmented Generation tool which allows users to interact with a large historic database of communications history.
- Topic modelling to: make oral histories searchable and to link collections from pairs of collections (Science Museum / National Museums Scotland / Discovery Museum)

- Fine-tuned an embeddings model to connect collections objects from National Museums Scotland and Science Museum Group using multimodal linkage – allowing for shared collections metadata across institutions.
- Large Multimodal Models (LMMs), including LLava, to: generate descriptions based on films and other images; linking images with other images or text based on similarity scores.
- Multimodal models to link collections objects between institutions.

These are explained in the context of the investigations in the annex.

10. To nurture dialogue in the digital humanities space between heritage/ humanities and data/computation.

See 4 and 8 above. In recognising the under-explored research potential of cultural heritage and collections data, the wider TaNC agenda implicitly requires that critical questions be addressed concerning where material culture is situated within the research culture of the humanities broadly and Digital Humanities specifically. These were inevitably encountered in the course of work on *Congruence Engine*, and may be productively examined in the context of envisioning systemic change that is enabled by the Action Research methodology. They include the distinct cultures of academic and curatorial practice and how both the potential of novel digital methods and the mediation effected by a social machine (designed for purposes of UK collections linkage by diverse communities of interest) may erode or bridge these. Broader questions too are raised and are being considered around resistance to unfamiliar methods and frameworks of operation, and legitimate concerns for ownership in developing data, the maintenance of professional status, and traditions of validation in knowledge production.

11. To work with other Discovery projects and AHRC to maximise the benefits and legacy of TaNC.

This laudable ambition is discussed in section 11.

4. Partnership Structure

Funded Partners

- Science Museum Group, base for Principal Investigator (PI) Tim Boon, Research Support Officer Carol Chung, Project Coordinator Katerina Webb-Bourne, and Co-Investigators (Co-Is): Alex Butterworth, John Stack, Jamie Unwin and Dave Patten; Research Fellows: Stefania Zardini-Lacedelli, Max Long, Cameron Tailford, Daniel Belteki, Daniel Wilson, Natasha Kitcher, Felix Needham-Simpson, Sarah Middle, Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi, Jo Kent, Alex Fitzpatrick, Julia Ankenbrand. Curators: Alexandra Rose, Ben Russell, Oliver Carpenter.
- University College London, base for Co-I Jon Agar (Communications history)
- University of Leeds, base for Co-I: Helen Graham and Research Fellow (later Co-I) Arran Rees (Action Research), and Co-Is Simon Popple (Digital Community engagement) and Graeme Gooday (Energy History)
- Liverpool University, base for Co-I William Ashworth (Textiles history)
- School of Advanced Study, University of London, base for Co-I Jane Winters and Research Fellow Anna-Maria Sichani (Digital Humanities), data scientists Kunika Kono and Kaspar Beelen, Beatrice Canelli
- Historic England, base for Co-I Matt Bristow and (previously) Wayne Cocroft (Historic Environment)
- British Film Institute, base for Co-I Patrick Russell (Film); Stephen McConnachie, Steve Foxon and Ros Cranston
- National Museums Scotland, base for Co-I Geoff Belknap (Communications history)
- Bradford Industrial Museum, Collaborating Organisation, base for Lizzie Llabres and Lauren Padgett (Textiles history)
- Discovery Museum, Collaborating Organisation, base for Kylea Little and Bernard Musesengwe (Energy history)
- Manchester Digital Laboratory, base for Asa Calow (Data science)
- Wikimedia UK, base for Stuart Prior and Daria Cybulska (interactions and collaborations over Wikidata)

We also let contracts with:

- University of Sussex TAGLab (involvement in NERF and data field alignment investigations)
- Flax and Teal (specialist contractors for work on Arches content management system)

Unfunded Project Partners (data providers and collaborators), with areas of active participation

- 509 Arts (involvement in oral histories investigation and Bradford Convergence)
- BBC History and Heritage / Programme Index (involvement in early discussions)
- Birmingham Museums Trust (involvement in Journal special issue)
- Bradford Sound Systems: Rites of Passage (involvement in oral histories investigations)

- BT Archives (involvement in Communications investigation, including on Researchers' notes and documentary narrative to catalogue entry)
- Grace's Guide to Industrial History (data involved in several investigations)
- History of Science Society: Isis Bibliography (involvement in literature investigation)
- National Coal Mining Museum
- National Museum Wales (early involvement)
- National Museums of Northern Ireland (involvement in textiles investigation)
- Saltaire World Heritage Education Association (involvement in textiles investigation)
- Society for the History of Technology Bibliography (involvement in literature investigation)
- The National Archives (early involvement)
- The National Trust (involvement in textiles investigation)
- Tools of Knowledge Project (techniques and personnel contributed across the project)
- University of Leicester (involvement in oral history investigations and trade directories)
- Victoria and Albert Museum (involvement in textiles investigation)
- West Yorkshire Archaeological Service/Historic Environment Record (involved in textile investigations)

Individual Contracted Collaborators

- Alexander Appleton
- Jonathan Ainsworth
- Cal Murphy Barton
- Beatrice Cannelli
- Paul Craddock
- Gyanateet Dutta
- Yuan Gao
- Sam Griffiths
- Ciaran Johnson
- Jayne Knight
- Andy Mabbett
- Alexander Neish
- Denice Penrose
- Jennifer Reid
- Andrew Richardson
- Sara Romiti
- Stef de Sabbata
- Tim Smith
- Jennie Williams

Bradford Convergence Collaborators

- Aire Rivers Trust
- Bradford 2025

- Bradford Movie Makers
- Elaine Evans (Yorkshire Fashion Archive)
- Friends of Bradford's Becks
- Josh Jones (National Science and Media Museum)
- Judith Simpson (Bradford Movie Makers)
- Karol Wyszynski
- Leeds City Museum Bradford Council
- Marco Maison (Northumbria University)
- Martha Kean
- Paula Truman
- Rosie Freeman
- Ross Horsley
- Susan Waltham
- West Yorkshire Joint Services
- West Yorkshire Queer Stories
- William Gaunt (Sunny Bank Mills)
- Yorkshire Water

Steering Group

- Tilly Blyth
- Keri Facer
- David Gilbert
- Melissa Terras

Internal Project Board

- Tilly Blyth
- Tim Boon
- Jessica Bradford
- Rosie Cardiff
- Carol Chung
- Charlotte Connelly
- Paula Gill
- Helen Graham
- Sally MacDonald
- Arran Rees
- Lauren Ryall-Waite
- John Stack
- Katerina Webb-Bourne

5. Staffing Structure

Each of the original eight work packages was the responsibility of one lead investigator (some with other investigators), and most had an associated research fellow.

We resolved early staffing challenges by combining the Project Management function with the Action Research, achieving an agile and effective way of managing the project. *Congruence Engine's* capacity to address its objectives in a data-intensive and digital-focussed manner was transformed by the appointment of Alex Butterworth as Project Lead, Digital History; his understanding of digital history enabled us to make several more appointments on the digital side: Felix Needham-Simpson (Research Assistant: Data Wrangling and Development), Sarah Middle (ontologist), Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi and Jo Kent (data scientists). The School of Advanced Study has also contributed the services of digital specialists, Kunika Kono and Kaspar Beelen. We were fortunate after the tragic early death of Research Fellow Cameron Tailford to recruit Daniel Belteki in his place. The departure of Daniel Wilson to a long-term role at the Turing Institute made space for Natasha Kitcher to become Research Fellow for the Communications strand. Maternity leave enabled the appointment of Max Long to work on the textiles strand, and underspend elsewhere meant that we could employ participation and engagement professionals Alex FitzPatrick and Julia Ankenbrand to facilitate the Bradford convergence and associated project outputs.

Below are the top line research question for each (some edited reflecting development within the project) with those primarily responsible. After the combining of project management and action research, and especially after the transition into the 'second era' stage of multiple investigations applying specific digital techniques, the Action Research-ARPM group took overall charge of the sequencing and oversight of work, with the responsible individuals listed continuing to have oversight of their particular areas.

Umbrella WP1: Tim Boon, PI

- How may we use computational techniques to enable linkage between UK industrial history collections of all kinds and scales for historical and curatorial purposes?

Digital History WP2: Alex Butterworth with John Stack (SMG oversight until his departure for the National Gallery in 2024)

- How can we apply machine learning and other computational techniques to support real-world historical enquiry? How does digital mediation - and the digitalisation of methods - change historical practice, including the narratives historians and others may construct? What considerations should inform the design of interfaces, of all kinds (visualisation, haptic, etc), to historical data?

Digital Humanities WP3: Jane Winters; Research Fellow, Anna-Maria Sichani

- How do technology choices affect research processes and introduce biases, with what ethical implications? What skills are needed to equip the creators of the National Collection, and how can these be acquired? What infrastructures are required, including for data management?

Participatory Action Research WP4. Including race and decolonisation group and Bradford convergence: Helen Graham; Research Fellow (later Co-Investigator) Arran Rees, Research Fellows: Alex Fitzpatrick and Julia Ankenbrand. Katerina Webb-Bourne; co-facilitator for race and decolonisation working group.

- How can systemic action research technique be used to understand the challenges of realising a national collection of industrial history?

Digital exhibit WP5: First iteration: Tim Boon with Common Films; final iteration: Natasha Kitcher (research), Michael Beigel (Interpretation Manager) and Natasha Waterson (Project Management), overseeing Stamen Design.

- How can we best use digital exhibits in museum contexts to present data and narratives in a way that enables visitors to engage with, and the project to gain insights into public interest in, the project's objectives?

Historical / curatorial WPs 6-8:

- How does attention to assemblages of data on heterogeneous heritage items – objects, pictures, archives, films, TV and radio programmes, recordings, buildings, maps, places, etc – treated as historical sources – affect the historical narratives that historians, communities and curators may construct?

Textiles: Will Ashworth; Research Fellows, Stefania Zardini-Lacedelli and Max Long; associated museum: Bradford Industrial Museum (Lizzie Llabres, Lauren Padgett)

Energy: Graeme Gooday; Research Fellows, Cameron Tailford, Daniel Belteki; associated museum: Discovery Museum Newcastle (Kylea Little, Bernard Musesengwe)

Communications: Jon Agar; Research Fellows, Daniel Wilson, Natasha Kitcher; associated museum: National Museums Scotland (Geoff Belknap)

Although we started the project using a working group model, supported by the BaseCamp project management tool, that allowed investigators and researchers to set up organising structures as they needed, we moved away from this approach. We dedicated time, at the beginning, to making space for divergence, as well as congruence of views and approaches. We did this to enable parallel and distributed action, led by those motivated by the topic of the working groups, in a loosely bounded, but centrally charted, environment to help unleash people's potential to innovate – both practically and conceptually. After about nine months, we noted that the working groups were not as dynamic as we had hoped they might be, and that meetings and actions were happening more informally than at a working group level. So, to really start cohering a sense of collective understanding of that work, we decided to use more active facilitation methods. Our new meetings ecology – discussed in more detail in the research approach section (8) – aimed to cohere all the investigations. In doing this, we sought to invite the multiple parallel investigations into conversation with a group of people who, in turn, would notice crossovers, emergent challenges and opportunities, and develop the sense of collective understanding about the findings of project. (We retained BaseCamp for broad whole project communications, but we found our Notion Wiki, adopted at the end of the first year, more valuable for project communication and documentation of our activity.)

Figure 1: Notion landing page

6. Overall Programme

Figure 2: Overall programme at stage of second report.

Figure 3: Overall programme as delivered.

7. Events and Presentations

Date	Name / Title	Type	Person / People	Audience	Audience type	URL
20-Oct-21	The Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories	Postaward Presentation	Tim Boon	50	SMG Collections Team	
28-Jan-22	The Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories: SMG All Staff Briefing	Event	Tim Boon	300	SMG All Staff	
Dec-21	Project Webpage Created	Website			General	https://www.sciencemuseumgroup.org.uk/projects/the-congruence-engine
Jan-22	Project Blog Created	Website			General	https://ceblog.sciencemuseumgroup.org.uk/
01-Feb-22	Boon, Tim. "The Congruence Engine." Viewpoint (BSHS Magazine), no. 126, Feb. 2022, pp. 8–9.	Publication	Tim Boon	500	Members of the British Society for the History of Science	https://www.bshs.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/No-126-Feb-2022-for-web.pdf
9-11-Feb-22	Congruence Engine Opening Conference	Event		50	Co-Is, Project Partners, Project Board, Steering Committee	
Mar-22	Project Basecamp	Website		50	Co-Is, Project Partners, Project Board, Steering Committee	https://3.basecamp.com/5316423/projects

20-21-Jun-22	Textiles Planning Workshop (Leeds)	Workshop		15	Co-Is and Project Partners for Textiles, CE SMG Team	The textiles pilot workshop, 20/21 June, Leeds (basecamp.com)
22-Jul-22	The Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories: Session at Annual Conference of the British Society for the History of Science, Belfast	Event	Tim Boon	40	BSHS delegates: historians of science and technology	
27-Jul-22	Textiles Reflection and Planning Workshop (London)	Workshop		15	Co-Is and Project Partners for Textiles, CE SMG Team	
20-21 Oct 22	Textiles Planning Workshop (Manchester)	Workshop		22	Co-Is, Project Partners and Participants for Textiles, CE SMG Team	
17-18 Nov 22	Science Museum Group Research Conference 2022	Workshop, Panel		150	SMG staff, Postgraduate students of Science and Technology, CE Co-Is and project partners for Textiles	
17-20 Nov 22	The Congruence Engine: New Techniques to Link Collections for HSTM: HSS Annual Meeting 2022	Event	Rebekah Higgitt	300	HSS Members, Academic Historians of Science	
Autumn 2022	Congruence Engine, Science Museum Group Journal	Journal Special Issue		5,748	Museum curators,	Autumn 2022 - Science Museum Group Journal

					academics, students	
19-Jan-23	The Congruence Engine: Digital Tools for New Collections-Based Industrial Histories, NRM Science Museum Group Staff Briefing	Presentation	Tim Boon	100	SMG NRM Staff	
6-7 Mar -23	UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure Community Congress (Birmingham)	Event	Anna Maria Sichani	150	Academics, Researchers, Digital professionals	
23-Mar-23	Reframing Failure: It's Complicated - Collaborations and Partnerships (online)	Panel	Arran Rees and Helen Graham	25	SAS delegates, Digital Humanities academics and professionals	
27-28 Mar 23	Social Machine Workshop (Newcastle)	Workshop		23	Co-Is, Project Partners (BFI), CE SMG Team	
29-Jun-23	'Technical Museum Collections as if Science Studies Matters', STS Italia Conference 2023, Bologna	Presentation	Tim Boon	20	Academics, Professional Historians	
30-Jun-23	Project Blog Updated (New Pages)	Website		6,040 Article Views (to date)	General	https://ceblog.science.museumgroup.org.uk/
10-14 July 23	Digital Humanities Conference (Graz)	Presentation	Anna Maria Sichani, Arran Rees, Stefania Zardini Lacedelli	40	Academics, Historians, Digital Professionals	
03-Aug-23	Heritage Connector and Congruence Engine (SMG London)	Workshop		23	Co-Is, Project Partners (HC +CE), CE SMG Team, Digital Professionals	

31-Aug-23	White Rose Doctoral Training Consortium (Leeds)	Presentation	Arran Rees	60	PhD Students	
27-30-Sep-23	'A Future For Our Past: 25th International Conference On Industrial Heritage' INCUNA (Gijón, Spain)	Presentation	Daniel Belteki and Graeme Gooday	40	Academics, Historians, Industrial Heritage Professionals	
05-Oct-23	Collections Trust Conference (Online)	Presentation	Arran Rees	100	Academics, Researchers, Digital professionals	
27-Oct-23	Bradford Convergence Workshop (SMG London)	Workshop		23	Co-Is, CE SMG Team, Project Partners (Wikimedia/BFI)	
Oct 2023 - Feb 2024	The Congruence Engine Project Exhibit, Discovery Museum	Exhibit		c.18,000	General	The Congruence Engine Project What's On Discovery Museum
7-9-Nov-23	National Centre for Research Methods E-Festival (Online)	Presentation	Will Ashworth	40	Academics, Researchers, Digital professionals	
09-Nov-23	Visualising Oral histories Workshop (Leicester)	Workshop		16	Co-Is, Project Partners, Participants (Uni Of Leicester), CE SMG Team	
15-17-Nov-23	RO.ME Museum Exhibition (Rome)	Presentation	Arran Rees	35	Museum Professionals	
22-Nov-23	Work In Progress Seminar (Leeds)	Presentation	Arran Rees and Helen Graham	15	Academics	

20-Dec-24	Congruence Engine Newsletter Year Two	Publication		48	Co-Is, Project Partners, Research Fellows, SMG Team	
09-Jan-24	Moving Images Materials Workshop (BFI)	Workshop		15	Co-Is, Project Partners and Participants (Discovery Museum), CE SMG Team	
23-Jan-24	Cross-TaNC Ethics Workshop	Workshop	Anna Maria Sichani, Arran Rees, Alex Fitzpatrick	22	TaNC Discovery Project Partners	
13-Feb-24	Bluegrass Evaluation Event (Discovery Museum Exhibit)	Event		27	Local historians	
14-Feb-24	Generative AI Workshop	Workshop		15	Co-Is, Project Partners and Participants (Leeds Uni), CE SMG Team	
19-Feb-24	Collections as Data: Collaborating across data spaces for cultural heritage and open science	Workshop, Presentation	Anna-Maria Sichani	50	GLAM Professionals and Academics (EU & UK)	https://www.dariah.eu/event/collections-as-data-collaborating-across-data-spaces-for-cultural-heritage-and-open-science/
28-Feb-24	TaNC Discovery Project Webinar Series	Webinar	Nayomi Kasthuriarachchi, Natasha Kitcher	130	GLAM Professionals and Academics	
19-Mar-24	TaNC Discovery Project Webinar Series: Heritage Data Practices & Decentralisation	Webinar	Anna-Maria Sichani	120	GLAM Professionals and Academics	https://www.nationalcollection.org.uk/events/webinars/heritage-

						data-practices-decentralisation
05-May-24	TaNC Discovery Project webinar: Research Methods & Ethics	Webinar	Arran Rees	c. 100	GLAM Professionals and Academics	https://www.nationalcollection.org.uk/events/webinars/research-methods-ethics-connecting-uk-heritage-data
15-May-24	Locating Photographs, Bradford Convergence	Workshop	Natasha Kitcher, Daniel Belteki	10	Local Heritage Researchers and Professionals, Project Partners	
16-May-24	Geo-locating millponds and waterways, Bradford Convergence	Workshop	Max Long, Daniel Belteki	15	Waterways Professionals and Academics, Local Heritage Researchers and Professionals, Project Partners	
17-May-24	Connecting Oral Histories, Bradford Convergence	Workshop	Julia Ankenbrand, Alex Butterworth, Arran Rees, Stefania Zardini Lacedelli	15	Local Heritage Researchers and Professionals, Project Partners	
20-May-24	Tracing story of Bradford's becks and river pollution' - article in Telegraph and Argus	Newspaper Article	Max Long	500	Local Residents in Bradford, Readers of Telegraph and Argus	https://perma.cc/2H92-QM9M
25-May-24	Becks Pollution Public event, Bradford Convergence	Event	Natasha Kitcher, Max Long	30	Museum Visitors	

25-May-24	Once Upon a Sheep film screening, Bradford Convergence	Workshop	Max Long	30	Local Heritage Researchers and Professionals, Project Partners, General Public	
30-May-24	'Together': Interdisciplinarity, collaboration and participation in digital cultural heritage research. The case of the Congruence Engine project.	Journal Article (Submission)	Anna Maria Sichani, Arran Rees, Stefania Zardini Lacedelli		GLAM Professionals and Academics	
05-Jun-24	UK-IE Digital Humanities Association Annual Event (Cork, Ireland) Living diversity in interdisciplinary collaborative research in digital cultural heritage: Lessons learned from the 'Congruence Engine' project	Conference	Anna-Maria Sichani, Julia Ankenbrand, Nayomi Kasthuriarachchi, Natasha Kitcher, Daniel Belteki, Alex Fitzpatrick	50	GLAM Professionals, Digital Humanities Academics	https://digitalhumanities-uk-ie.org/2024-annual-event/
09-Jun-24	A toolkit for Generative AI, data protection and intellectual property in digital cultural heritage A toolkit for Generative AI, data protection and intellectual property in digital cultural heritage	Toolkit	Anna-Maria Sichani		GLAM Professionals and Academics	https://sas-dhrh.github.io/genai-cch-toolkit/
27-Jun-24	Paper Congruence Engine and the Linking of Archaic Museum Data to Lustre Workshop 4: The Future of AI to Unlock Digital Records	Conference	Tim Boon	30	GLAM Professionals and Academics	https://lustre-network.net/event/the-future-of-ai-to-unlock-digital-records/
27-Jun-24	Digital Preservation for the Arts, Social Sciences and Humanities Conference	Conference/presentation & workshop	Anna-Maria Sichani, Daniel Belteki, Arran Rees	75	GLAM Professionals and Academics	https://dpassh.org/programme-2024/

11-Jul-24	BSHS Conference, two panels entitled 'Congruence Engine: Digital tools for new collections based industrial histories'	Conference	Tim Boon, Natasha Kitcher, Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi, Max Long, Daniel Belteki, Jon Agar, Rebekah Higgitt, Graeme Gooday, Geoff Belknap	60	Academics, Researchers and Museum Professionals	https://www.bshs.org.uk/
12-Jul-24	Panel presentation on CE work, for panel 'Engaged histories: who listens to modern British history and what do they hear?', alongside Sundeep Lidher, Holly Smith. Chaired by Lucy Delap. Part of New York-Cambridge Training Collaboration (NYCTC) in Modern British History	Conference	Max Long	40	Academics	https://nyctc.history.columbia.edu/
18-Jul-24	TaNC Data Documentation focus group meeting	Workshop	Anna-Maria Sichani, Katerina Webb-Bourne	10	TaNC Discovery Project Partners	
04-Sep-24	Rutherford, A., Sichani, A.-M., Foxton, K., & Perry, S. (2024). Ethics as Practice: Report on the 1st Discovery Project Ethics Workshop. Towards a National Collection.	Report	Anna-Maria Sichani	589 views / 457 downloads (as of 29/10/2024)		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13683142
09-Sep-24	Wikipedia-thon Saltaire Collection	Workshop	Alex Fitzpatrick, Julia Ankenbrand	10	Local Heritage Researchers and Professionals, Project Partners, General Public	

24-Sep-24	Slavery and Steam Workshop (York)	Workshop	Alex Fitzpatrick, Arran Rees, Katerina Webb-Bourne	17	GLAM Professionals and Academics	
03-Oct-24	Panel presentation: "What skills does the sector need to develop to support increased use of, and access to, collections data?" Collections Trust Conference	Conference	Anna-Maria Sichani	300	GLAM Professionals and Academics	https://collectionstrust.org.uk/events/2024-conference/conference-2024-programme/
03-Oct-24	Panel presentation: "Discussion – how will having greater access to collections data be a gamechanger for the sector?" Collections Trust Conference	Conference	Arran Rees	300	GLAM Professionals and Academics	
13-15-Oct-24	Artefacts XXIX/Congruence Engine Final Conference: New Digital Practices for Science and Technology Collections	Conference	Co-Is, Project Partners, Research Fellows, SMG Team	250	GLAM Professionals, Academics, Researchers, Digital Professionals	
19-Nov-24	Presentation - OA materials in the GLAM sector at the 'Third-party materials in OA publishing' webinar	Webinar	Arran Rees	100	GLAM Professionals and Academics	
29-Oct-24	Hawkins, A., & Sichani, A. M. (2024). 'Data Matters': Report on the Towards a National Collection Discovery Projects focus group on data management, documentation, and archiving practices in digital cultural heritage projects. Towards a National Collection.	Report	Anna-Maria Sichani			https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006955

20-21-Nov-24	Towards a National Collection Two-Day Conference 2024	Plenary, Presentations, Demos, Performance	Co-Is, Project Partners, Research Fellows		GLAM Professionals, Academics, Researchers, Digital Professionals	Towards a National Collection Two-Day Conference 2024 Towards a National Collection
22-Nov-24	Book chapter: 'Doing, failing, learning: understanding what didn't work as a key research finding in action research', in Reframing Failure (eds.) Michael Donnay and Anna-Maria Sichani		Publication	Arran Rees	GLAM Professionals, Academics, Researchers, Digital Professionals	
27-Nov-24	Reflections on History of AI	Research Seminar	Jon Agar	20	Academics	https://warwick.ac.uk/arts/history/research/researchseminar2024-25/
Jan-25	Staff briefings to SMG and its several museums	Briefings	Tim Boon	100s	Science Museum Group staff	

8. Research Approach⁴

We managed *Congruence Engine* using a systemic action research approach designed to enable the investigation of complexity and whole system change. The central philosophy of action research is to value practical as well as theoretical knowledge – ‘the creative action of people to address issues that matter to them’.⁵ Like many participatory projects delivered under the 2010s-era AHRC-led ‘Connected Communities’ theme, *Congruence Engine* included multiple participants: investigators, researchers, partners and community-based groups and individuals. It took a distinctively *systemic* action research methodology to make this possible.⁶ Here we were influenced by Danny Burns’ elaborations of systemic approaches to action research, which offer practical ways to design participatory research at scale in ways that enable different parallel investigations and crosscutting events to draw together the insights they produce.⁷ Design principles common to many strands of action research were: Multiple perspectives – we cannot understand the complexity of barriers to accessing and using collections only from the academic perspective; we must allow for a plurality of motivations and experiences;⁸ Value different ways of knowing – all are intrinsically valuable; in our endeavour we need the experiential and affective as much as specific empirical knowledge;⁹ Learn together through doing – we cannot understand challenges to establishing the linked data resource for industrial history we propose only in a theoretical way; we need to try, test and push the systems that already exist to work out how they can change.¹⁰

To these principles systemic action research adds: An improvisatory approach to change – real benefits come from being responsive to, and working with, what arises through the enquiry process (rather than sticking to a fixed plan); Going where the energy is – people being able to work on what has urgency and meaning for them is powerful; Divergence and Convergence – in a large interdisciplinary team we needed to make space for people to be able to pursue their specific technical or historical interests and also bring the insights generated together to create shared meaning. The action research methodology, as well as enabling the research, collectively convened all of us as participants to collaboratively trace, document and develop the project, evaluating barriers encountered. It constantly addressed, interrogated and refined the formulation and value of the project aim also quoted in Section 3: ‘via an action research methodology to use real-world historical enquiries of community-, museum- and university-based historians and curators to hone digital tools needed for proof of concept of a linked national collection, using the example of industrial history’.

Drawing on an end of project reflective process – which we termed ‘End of Project Conversations’ – we have recognised that the strength in our action research design lay primarily in enabling the self-organising investigations that formed the major part of the research process. But, in *Congruence Engine*, as in most big projects, complex power dynamics were at play, produced by the varying seniority, contract type as well as gender and sexuality, race and class of team members. For future projects, we would recommend recognition of such potential dynamics and their management via consistent group work processes to accompany the project’s divergent approach.

The Project’s Course

The project’s funding application case for support, alongside its commitment to action research, also included a proposed meta-structure for managing its delivery. The initial plan was that, after project startup, we would have three successive major nine-month cycles of research, one for each of our chosen industrial

sectors: textiles, energy and communications, each one featuring two workshops (see figure 2). In a conventional project we could have insisted on these, but the beauty of the action research approach was that it enabled the research to go ‘where it wanted to go’, and where it wanted to go was not into three near-identical investigations of equal duration into three sectors. The action research methodology enabled us to be attentive to many things that we could not have known at the start. Looking back, it is possible to discern four *Congruence Engine* ‘eras’ (see figure 3): For much of 2022 we started from ‘walking alongside’ small investigations and moved to researcher-led investigations. The next era took us from these hand-stitched ‘mini-investigations’ to bigger data and intensive use of digital tools (late 2022 to mid-2024). The third moved us mainly from investigations-centred activity overlappingly to community-centred activity (our ‘Bradford convergence’), mainly complete by July 2024.¹¹ Finally, we moved away from that activity to articulation in the project’s outputs. In the midst of this, we did not entirely reject the planned sequence of work, but the textiles history cycle was, in the event, overlappingly followed by that on energy, and work on communications also began in parallel with both of the others, with all being pursued until the end of the third ‘era’. In part this was because we learned in year one that working digitally at scale would require longer timescales than our initial planning could manage (not least because of the need to appoint new digitally capable staff, and to let small contracts, before some kinds of work could be undertaken). This shift in approach was because the larger concern of ensuring that the project was really addressing the funding’s core concerns with enabling digital linkage of collections was more important than evenness of attention to three arbitrarily chosen sectors. And the reason, in turn, for that is that the whole purpose of *Congruence Engine*, although its subject has been industrial history, is to show how collections of any kind may be linked to enable greater access to, and enjoyment of, what is held in heritage collections on the public’s behalf across the country.

What started as the ‘textiles pilot’ in the project’s first ‘era’ developed into the textiles strand of the project, across four workshops, developing investigation ideas in dialogue with community and sector partners. Whilst several of the later investigations were seeded at these workshops, we found that, as we have said, the investigations were focusing on what we referred to as the ‘hand-stitched’ level of work; small scale examples of how connections between discrete subsets of data might help bring about new insights for historians, amateur and professional. They certainly linked collections items and historical practice, but they were closer to standard historical practice than to the specifically digital methods and the larger scale that we needed to investigate. All the same, working through the pipelines of this kind of work is important for understanding the different ways people will approach working with collections items from across the UK, and reveals areas where particular kinds of technological support or intervention are productive.

To support our work, we combined the action research and project management aspects of the project and developed a new meetings ecology to support the multiple pipeline investigations that were ongoing. At weekly ‘Action Research Project Management’ (ARPM) meetings, a core of investigators and project management staff attended to urgent matters of project governance and progress. At fortnightly Investigations Meetings, those responsible for the individual investigations (mainly the Research Fellows) brought their proposals and research in progress to be guided; the meetings also oversaw the overall balance of the investigations. This was part of the work that encouraged interdisciplinarity. The humanities-trained researchers were able to become competent in technical work whilst the discussions and investigations also provided more humanities-grounded context to the digital-focused researchers collaborating with them. These meetings were complemented by attendance at digital drop-in sessions in the alternating weeks that created space for researchers leading investigations to talk through and learn

more about potential digital tools; these meetings also served to identify further training needs that could be addressed on a quick-turnaround basis.

Publication in early 2023 of the *Congruence Engine* special issue of the *Science Museum Group Journal* more or less as we switched from the small data scale to the large, was a major project milestone, with its 18 contributions by 28 authors.¹² The writing of the journal was conceived as a part of the action research, rather than simply as an output. In composing it, different constellations of project researchers interacted and collaborated to make sense of the work that the project's first year had done. The authors experimented with different ways of knowing and knowledge production, producing traditional single-authored pieces charting the different connections being made, collaborative dialogic pieces, and visually led photographic and film essays.

During that first era, the project team became acutely aware of the need to work with larger datasets, heterogeneous data, and to use novel machine learning techniques more actively. We took the three-month period from November 2022 to reflect, re-organise and re-orientate based on the learning from the first year; this was the transition to the 'second era'. Small data 'hand-stitched' investigations close to standard historical practice were unable to address the collections-linking ambitions of the project (and the TaNC funding). In the same period, the project was able to increase digital historian Alex Butterworth's time on the project and he became a Co-Investigator with the job title Project Lead, Digital History. Across the project we have been interested to explore the necessarily interdisciplinary space between humanities research, museum practice and data science technique. Not formally a data scientist, Butterworth came to the project already a hybrid individual with digital skills motivated by a developed historical sense. Core roles for him were to highlight potentials for working at scale with data and with digital tools, and involvement in recruitment of new staff members and contractors from the data science community.

Through this period of reflection and planning forward, the project sharpened its digital through-line and surfaced the pipeline processes that the investigations would experiment with. The core process under investigation was how to create machine-readable linkable heritage data from catalogue records and archive materials and then to use that data to explore collections linkage. We used different tools, methods and techniques to move material down the pipeline, depending on its initial state (for example, an analogue printed catalogue or a collection of digital oral histories). This sharpened approach, supported by the fortnightly Investigation meetings and digital drop-in sessions, constituted a digital re-balancing of the project. Alongside the reflective and re-organising work, and in acknowledgement of the difficulties in recruiting specific digital expertise, the project arranged a responsive hiring model within the Science Museum Group that resulted in the recruitment of flexible digital-focused roles, and contracts with organisations, both serving to contribute to and enhance the digital innovation work of the investigations.

Informed by our reflections on the first phase of the project, at a workshop in Newcastle in March 2023, the core project team decided to adopt the social machine metaphor, and this was followed by the presentation at the Towards a National Collection (TaNC) conference in April 2023 of a general vision for a united digital collection as created by a social machine.¹³ Enabled by the action research approach, *Congruence Engine* self-consciously set out to model the kinds of activity that we speculated would be involved in developing a collections-linking digital resource for curatorship and history. We worked via multiple investigations, that eventually numbered more than 40 (see annex), with the aim of exploring the field. Our aim of also drawing together a 'design specification' from the social and technical requirements we would uncover along the way was not, as we had anticipated, requested for composition of TaNC's overall infrastructure

recommendations.¹⁴ This has the advantage for us that we will be able to assemble these in a reflective manner once the project is complete, in the second, and shorter, of our two project books.¹⁵

The ways that we pursued the multiple investigations we conducted were informed by our lead metaphor of ‘the national collection as a social machine’; it embodied the ‘verbed’ approach that sees UK collections linkage as being as much an activity as a thing. Each individual investigation ran through action research cycles of planning, action, observation, reflection, and coming back to the investigation meetings for discussion, advice and steering. These cycles of activity and interaction into which the investigations meetings and digital drop-ins repeatedly fed, developed understanding of the interactions between people and digital programs – the ‘social machine’ – iteratively helping us to specify its technical and social requirements. Enabled by our systemic action research approach, the variety of different investigations enabled the project to work through micro- and macro- understandings of how researchers might operate within digitally linked UK collections, and how a process of creating such linkage can operate as a social machine. An individual investigation acts as a case study of how a researcher might undertake research using parts of various UK collections, adopting a variety of different tools and datasets, and rehearsing sophisticated processes. Whilst their specific research might have been investigating a historical question pertinent to the individual researcher or project partner, they were also modelling different pipelines for heritage items to be transformed into heritage data, becoming part of a wider, increasingly interlinked, cultural heritage data landscape.

Mapping investigations and the pipeline											
Live investigations	Material artefact	Handwritten sources	Printed analogue material	Digitised text material	Image	Moving image	Audio	Machine readable data	Extractable databases	Annotated sources	Data model sources
Oral Histories as connective sources			Digitisation and OCR for non-machine readable transcriptions				Speech to text for non-transcribed audio	NER, topic modelling & sentiment analysis	Collection database searches with extracted entities	Annotated transcriptions, connecting objects, places, people and organisations	
Connecting workers' songs with mining and textile connections: a cross-strand investigation.			Digitisation and OCR for non-machine readable lyric/music sheets			Speech to text for non-transcribed video recordings	Speech to text for non-transcribed audio	Dialect translation, participatory metadata enrichment, NER, topic modelling & sentiment analysis	Collection database searches with extracted entities		
Neural Radiance Field / Heritage Sites as Lost Mills sub-investigation					NeRF on photos of mills	Segmenting moving image into a series of stills				Geolocated 3D model of mills and spaces	
The Power of Advertisements					Segmenting and cropping images from digitised magazines			Computer vision, image categorisation	Collection database searches with extracted entities	Annotated images, associated with objects, company records and accounts of gendered advertising	
Mapping Power Stations				OCR to make PDFs machine readable				NLP, mapping, data cleaning, geospatial plotting		Plotting and connecting collections records within geospatial polygons	
Deeper catalogue data				OCR to make PDFs machine readable				Ngrams and Surprising phrases analysis			
Museum online catalogues-as-data				Museum catalogue data exports				Identifying and defining rich & thin records and the (mis)use of taxonomies	Comparing with other museum catalogue exports		
Industrial occupations				Scraping of Occupations list website				Organising data in a tabulated format and clean	connect with and review in relation to other taxonomical style data		industrial occupations ontology aiding the description of connective relationships
Segmenting and abstracting trade directory data											
No access											

Figure 4: Notion page tabulating how a selection of the investigations map to different aspects of pipelines between analogue collections items and linkable data.

Decolonising Industrial Heritage and Consciously Designing Anti-Oppressive Collections Linkage

Congruence Engine addressed race and decolonisation by turning the focus onto our core topic – industrial heritage – and ourselves, as a predominantly white project team.

Congruence Engine identified the implications of positioning industrial heritage as inextricably linked with colonisation, capitalist extraction and exploitation; that the material remains of the UK's industrial past may be seen – amongst other things – as documents of colonialism and post-colonial societies. This strand of work was supported by a research discussion group, with relevant readings brought by each member from their own areas of disciplinary or professional expertise.¹⁶ These co-facilitated sessions were designed to enable participants to reflect on the ways this work could be distributed throughout the project and to see how questions raised in the discussions had potential implications for their investigations.

Central to this shifted focus was developing ways to address racism that were not based in inclusion and diversity paradigms. Rather than draw in Black and Brown people and groups in order to 'diversify' the project – which has been repeatedly shown to create extractive dynamics – we explored what could be gained by explicitly addressing whiteness. A small group of project members read Layla F Saad's *Me and White Supremacy* using the 'circle way' method, as suggested by the author.¹⁷

This work was put to the test during the Bradford convergence, a strand of collaborative experimentation between project members and people working on local heritage in Bradford. Here we took the opportunity to experiment with not practising extractive approaches or exposing Black and Brown collaborators to potential harm by bringing them into predominantly white spaces. Learning from this strand of work informed a more nuanced formulation of how to avoid accidentally feeding long-rehearsed diversity and inclusion logics when there isn't enough time and resource for actively anti-oppressive and anti-racist practice.

9. Research Results

Overall Implications

We argue that the ‘UK digital collection’ should in practice be a facilitative infrastructure for collections linkage, not a standalone digital collection. This linkage will use a linked open data approach to make collections items truly discoverable by reuniting them in digital space, thus enabling their cultural capital to be realised for social, cultural, economic and health benefits.

The agency for creating this collections linkage will need to be distributed between heritage organisations big and small and the practitioners often thought of merely as audiences (professional and lay) for what heritage organisations do. These organisations, groups and individuals will be empowered by the widespread and unprecedented availability of collections data to incorporate it in their practice, intensifying connections either as a direct intention, or as a side-effect, of their activity.

The infrastructure to achieve this will be a ‘mixed economy’ that works via a currency of open data. It will involve the collections management systems of heritage organisations alongside aggregators including the Museum Data Service and potentially the National Data Library. But it also needs minimal infrastructure including a simple data register and resource index to ensure that collections of every scale and ownership can be linked, alongside the data representing linkages that express the historical realities and narratives that link the different collections items.

Through-Argument about the Project

The argument that leads to those implications was laid out by *Congruence Engine*’s PI in his plenary speech to the TaNC conference in November 2024. This, slightly embellished, provides the basis of the remainder of this section.

A brief statement of this argument follows (and we afterwards extrapolate the more detailed argument from each assertion): We want to make all UK heritage collections fully accessible together, not just institution-by institution as now, to those who would use them. The means to achieve this are their digital records. But, because of the history of heritage organisations, our current records are ill-suited for this purpose: in the main, they are thin, inconsistent and isolate collections items from the contexts in which they make sense. In *Congruence Engine*, we have therefore experimentally created ways to link collections with historical data as well as with each other, techniques that in various ways overcome these weaknesses. Because the creation of useful collections linkage requires the agency of its potential users, and because computing techniques are fallible, UK collections linkage requires a social machine for the task: a human-technical approach that mobilises human motivation and thereby overcomes machine incapacities. Many of our techniques employ machine learning, with the result that we have within our grasp the capacity to overcome decades of limited investment in collection documentation. But, because we are using these techniques, we confront a series of ethical issues that demand to be researched, even as we press for the resources to create user interfaces and scalable prototypes for a future infrastructure, which together can reveal the potential of what we have glimpsed.

Our Purpose

Congruence Engine took the TaNC mandate and researched at the proof-of-concept level a wide variety of techniques that could be applied to make all UK heritage collections fully accessible together, not just institution-by institution as now, to those who would use them. The project has proceeded on the basis that to do good historical and curatorial work, it would be insufficient to simply connect museums to museums, or just archives to archives, for example. UK collections linkage worth having should work intermedially across repositories that hold: objects, documents, pictures, records of historic places and sound and moving image media relevant to any subject. In *Congruence Engine* that subject is industrial history, but what we have done will be relevant for any subject and any collection type.

Our ultimate target for *Congruence Engine* is that the techniques we have developed will be deployed to bring more people to the collections themselves, each visitor empowered to integrate collections into their historical pursuits. We are concerned that the term 'UK digital collection' that has, for the TaNC Directorate, replaced the previous term 'national collection' is also not quite right. Evidently 'national' risks being read as implying an (unintended) exceptionalism, even a chauvinistic nationalism. But it also implies an unsustainable limitation for industrial collections that have international histories. Our quarrel here is more with the suggestion of a national digital collection separate from its referents, the collections. It is important to us as heritage sector people that the collections-centred digital resource for history that we are proposing is not an alternative to contact with the material – real objects, places, pictures and documents, and the experiences created in the encounter with them. Rather, we are creating an invitation and a means for people to experience tangible and intangible heritage directly: to encourage visits to heritage collections on the basis of what they contain: to the stores and archives, museums, libraries, galleries, theatres and cinemas, even as we promote the new kinds of digitally enabled histories and curatorial practice that will use them.

From the grant application onwards, we have been clear that the core direct audience for *Congruence Engine* would be people interested in industrial history, in whatever way. We have been mainly concerned with amateur and professional historians and curators or archivists. But potential users of collections often do not know of the existence of collections relevant to their interests, or else they know they exist but cannot gain access to them.

Further down the line, the improvements we propose will benefit wider groups of people, including casual visitors to museums. *Congruence Engine's* end-of-project digital exhibit models this by addressing the visiting audience at the Science and Media Museum in Bradford. Here again we think that active amateur historians will be particularly interested, but we are also addressing people from West Yorkshire who will be attracted to explore the linked histories of where they live, as well as anyone excited to see how digital work can reveal collections and history. The principle is eminently extensible to other towns, regions and, indeed to the nation and beyond.

Figure 5: Prototype *Congruence Engine* digital exhibit. See also figure 7.

The means to achieve this ambition to make all UK heritage collections fully accessible together are their digital records. But, because of the history of heritage organisations, our current records are ill-suited for this purpose. Only catalogue records have the potential to make collections available to these users because virtually every heritage organisation has too large a collection to display everything, so much is in store. In the case of the Science Museum, for example, a positive decision was made seven decades ago to create a reserve collection. At present, that ‘reserve’ amounts to some 97% of the total collection. But, because of the history of heritage organisations, our current digital records are ill suited for this purpose of truly making collections available: in the main, they are thin, inconsistent and isolate collections items from the contexts in which they make sense.

- a. Many of our records derived from audit records are **thin**, by which we mean that their brevity often means that the descriptions lack significant details, such as purposes, associated names, places or accurate dates.
- b. Objects may be **inconsistently** recorded *within* a collection, perhaps because the curator lacks time to bring old records up to quality with those for new acquisitions. But the greater inconsistency is between different *kinds* of collections. Museums are different from archives and use different data standards. As we know, libraries gained a huge amount by the adoption of the MARC standard, itself the product of the application of computers, from 1965 onwards.¹⁸ Whilst museums have the Spectrum collections management standard, which is well adopted in the sector, there has been no universally adopted cataloguing or data standard, and this has resulted in inconsistent approaches to cataloguing and data.¹⁹

And because of heritage organisations' differing historical purposes, what has mattered to each of them – and therefore what is encoded in their data – has differed from organisation to organisation.

- c. But, from the interpretive point of view, the major weakness of data representing heritage items is that it **isolates collections items from the contexts in which they make sense**.

In museums, data represents single items rather than the collections in which they make relational sense to their curators, a loom in a textile machinery collection, for example. But, more than that, the very act of collecting removes an item from its social historical ecology, and puts it to work otherwise. Our loom, for example, ceased to be the working tool of individual weavers and became the representative of a stage in the historical development of weaving equipment.

Heritage organisations have records of items in their collections for two reasons: for audit and for access and interpretation. As for audit, these organisations need to know what they have, what its legal status is, and where it can be found. At the Science Museum, over decades collections were audited using record cards that carried minimal identifying information, good enough to distinguish one item from another, but little more. A century ago, the Museum separately had records for interpretive purposes: curators wrote definitive display labels for objects and, in the majority of cases, these were gathered together in printed catalogues with some interpretive introductory text. But when it 'computerised' its catalogue from the 1980s, the Science Museum – which is not unusual among its peers in this respect – used its audit records, not its catalogues. This is the original reason for the thin data that represents our objects online. Moving cataloguing information up the scale to full enhanced record status is an aim we constantly seek to address. But the funding to support this has always been difficult to find because museums and galleries properly favour expenditure on the displays seen by millions of visitors over the backroom work of cataloguing. This state of affairs has inevitably been reinforced over the last 40 years as UK museums and galleries have increasingly adopted the practices of commercial businesses, investing in the quality of the 'product' (the displays) not least as a response to reduced governmental funding. And it's worth stating that this problem of slight data is often much worse for the small museums that have even less money than the nationals. These heritage organisations may only hold audit level records, and their databases may only be for internal collections management purposes.

***Congruence Engine* Linkage Techniques**

In summary, the records we work with make it difficult for researchers to see these collections and to use the items within them as normal recourses for their investigations. That is especially true of object and media collections. The styles of digital historical work that use data most successfully are those where data has been made palatable to users, for example the vast historical newspaper corpora of the British Library. Another example would be family historians' use of census data via Ancestry and Find My Past. These latter commercial services first digitally reproduce analogue access to demographic data sources, then template specific practices around genealogy in such a way that has not happened with most other kinds of mass data: trade directories, for example, may have been digitised (notably Leicester University Library's collection), but they have not been datafied. And in neither case – the census or the directories – is the data yet widely or freely available in a form that makes it fully interoperable and free to use as public data should be.

In *Congruence Engine*, we have therefore experimentally created ways to link collections and historical data. Most investigations in *Congruence Engine* have been experiments as if we lived in a world of linkable open data: we have converted collections datasets from our 15 partners so that they can become linkable data,

and we have created datasets that enable collections of objects to speak to each other. I am referring here to what we called ‘connective tissue data’. To explain: It became clear to us that to make collections of all kinds linkable to each other required the ontological leap of counting the data *within* collections as part of the UK collection, be it currently analogue or digital. Along with Census data, trade directories were one of the inciting categories: because they list individuals, addresses, trades and businesses, they hold the data that can, potentially, associate people, work, machines, products, places and the rest. Historical individuals designated their occupations themselves for these directories and the Census; and this is especially powerful for linkage: To take one example from the project’s research, Susan Excell, a wool comber living in Saltaire from around 1900, can be expected to have used a ‘Noble Comb’, a particular kind of machine, locatable to a particular floor in Salt’s Mill, preserved in the Bradford Industrial Museum, and shown in historical photographs.²⁰ To be able to make those links at an individual level would be satisfying for a family historian. But potentially this can be done at the level of huge data: a dense filigree of connection incorporating millions of people and heritage collection items that could enable a subtle and detailed social history of people, work and machines.²¹

In 2022-3, in what may be seen retrospectively as the second in four major phases – or ‘eras’ – of the project, as we sought to make it more intrinsically digital, we increasingly replaced our initial language of assemblage and association of heritage collections with one specifically of their linkage, of linked (open) data. Our aim at this stage was to go beyond the scale of normal, case-study-based, historical work like the Susan Excell example, to enable finely textured research at the level of factory workforces, towns or regions. This required a return to the approach of our previous project under the TaNC funding, *Heritage Connector*, in that we were once again gathering datasets, extracting terms and using graph databases. Our aim has been that digital linkage of items across collections and with historical data would enable individual items to be reunited with their constituting contexts, returning the ‘orphan object’ back to the ‘family’ of its historical origins. And so, most of the project investigations explored differing ways of achieving linkage. Some of these are ‘live’ in that they exist ‘in the wild’ in online data and in museum collections management systems. An example here is the Wikidata taxonomy for textile machinery we have created. Others have been achieved by combination within temporary housing in graph databases of derivatives from datasets lent by our project partners. For example, starting with various unstructured sources relevant to industrial Bradford – including lists of historic mills, Census and directory-derived data – we have been working to develop methods to extract graphs of entities (such as people, machines, trades and places) and their relationships. We have been bringing these together in an expanding knowledge graph implemented in a Neo4j graph database. The idea is that this could serve as a sandpit for human validation, regularisation and then further linkage using additional data science methods. The aim is to produce an Arches data management system to model what a local, federated infrastructure might look like in practice. We are doing this in a way that is compatible with the use of this software by our partner Historic England.

In the context of *Congruence Engine* as a project devoted to proof-of-concept, we have been concerned to demonstrate multiple ways in which linkage could be effected. In terms of next steps, the techniques will be experimentally replicable via our GitHub pages (listed in the annex), but only at this stage by individuals and organisations possessed of the appropriate skills. Their widespread adoption will require, alongside personal enthusiasm and motivation, policymaking and investment to be in place. These themes are being explored in the project’s second book, which lays out and reflects upon the potential decentralised methodology for creating the collections-linking digital resource for industrial history that we have sketched within the project.²²

Social Machine

Because the creation of a useful linked collection requires the agency of its potential users, and because computing techniques are fallible, the creation of UK collections linkage requires a social machine for the task: a human-technical approach that mobilises human motivation and thereby overcomes machine incapacities. *Congruence Engine* was, from the beginning, designed to be responsive to what potential users of a linked data resource would want to do with it. As we have argued, we want our investigations to make available collections resources and digital techniques to historians and curators to enable and enrich the kinds of history and curatorial work they are able to practice. In part this is to create a more responsive, more democratic, model of access to collections, driven from the periphery of need rather than from the (financially constrained) centre of provision. The national collection is so numerous as to be infinitely deep and wide, given that most archives are only enumerated, and digitised, to the part level, not yet the piece, let alone to the level of datafying each piece. Our expectation is that linkage will occur where people want to do it; it is impossible that every datapoint could be linked, but where a need is felt, then it *can* be. It is our task to enable this.

We say that part of the motivation is democratic, but the other is practical: most of the work needed for the creation of interoperable heritage data is human labour. We put on one side for the moment the troubling issue of tech companies' use of cheap labour from the South to build their LLMs.²³ There remains a benign aspect of human labour closer to home. The simpler digital tools such as Regular Expressions and OpenRefine can speed the regularisation of messy data, but their work must be intimately directed by humans. And then, the more computing-intensive work such as topic modelling or prompt engineering for interaction with large language models is necessarily human work, drawing on expert knowledge, or even simply on the human common sense not reproducible by artificial intelligence programs. These 'intern' and 'cog' style AI techniques are only tools, good at pattern-matching, but as useless without human interaction as a screwdriver without a hand.²⁴

So-called Generative AI 'hallucinations' – and we have seen plenty of those, not least when ChatGPT valuably converting a tabulated list of Bradford woollen mills to computer-readable form inserted some entirely fictitious examples – are not incidental wrinkles about to be ironed-out by clever programming. They are intrinsic products of the faux intelligence of these machines. Humans in the loop are required to remove them, just as pre-Ford, mechanics had to file-down machine parts so that they would work together.

Altogether, that is why we say that a social machine is required for the creation of UK collections linkage. We need the speed of automation, but we need the person's occupancy of the human world to ensure its results make sense and are of value in that human world.

Machine Learning Techniques

We speak of overcoming decades of limited investment in cataloguing. I do need to state that, although at one level what we are proposing is a catch-up in documentation, in other ways the linked data solutions that we are proposing present an entirely new opportunity for realising the cultural capital of collections, which is effectively scarcely exploited at all currently.²⁵ In addition to simpler computational techniques such as Regular Expressions or OpenRefine, we have also extensively used Large Language Model technologies. With ChatGPT being released at the end of our first year, we were able – because the project's action research

methodology enabled this flexibility – to explore many possibilities that have arisen in the generative AI goldrush of the last two years.

On the side of text composition, the real power of text generative AI techniques is not at all in the automatic writing of closely argued historical scholarship, but in the vast speed-up in the creation of more functional prose for practical reasons. Investigations under the *Congruence Engine* umbrella have shown, for example, that, given a set of different commissioned researchers' notes on previously uncatalogued files, GPT can produce serviceable formatted catalogue descriptions. Or, again, film catalogue descriptions have been created from speech-to-text transcriptions of documentary film commentaries. If we are to standardise such digital pipelines, automation promises to enable more extensive cataloguing of collections, and therefore findability of collections items. The flat and uniformly formatted prose produced by generative AI programs is appropriate to such purposes in a way that would be purposeless in areas of interpretation that require human intention.

The project has employed both data scientists and humanities researchers. The way they have worked has shown the potential for the creation of hybrid individuals who have on the one hand curatorial and humanities instincts, and, on the other, a lived sense of what it means to work using data science techniques. For the techniques the *Congruence Engine* researchers have used, see annex.

Ethics

Especially because we used these techniques, we confront a series of ethical issues. As we have argued, many of the project's successes after November 2022, after the release of readily usable Generative AI programs, relied on these techniques. In the experimental space of a research project, we felt an imperative to explore the affordances of these new LLM-based techniques. Our experience shows that we confront several different kinds of moral danger in this work, which together counsel caution. Especially worrying for our current geopolitical ethics is the way that the recent and current development of LLM technologies echoes the exploitative and extractive practices of the colonialism and imperialism with which we are elsewhere seeking to come to terms.

- I. We recognise that the training up until now of large language models on internet materials may well amount to a form of copyright theft.
- II. We also know that selection of texts and images for this purpose has been indiscriminate, so that archaic terms and now offensive attitudes may well be reproduced in the outputs of these models.
- III. We certainly know that the 'stochastic parrot' techniques on which these technologies operate do not have the discernment of a human reader and that close human supervision will continue to be a necessity. How can this be provided in a non-exploitative way, especially given that we know about the export of moderation and data work to the global south?
- IV. We recognise that the environmental costs of running AI algorithms is high, in terms of water consumption, and especially of energy – to the extent that technology companies are buying-up the future outputs from whole wind farms, and are commissioning nuclear power stations.²⁶ This development risks running roughshod over the climate emergency measures to which our organisations are committed.
- V. Many wise people are counselling that we are occupying just the latest in a series of AI 'bubbles', associated with hype about both the dangers and the capabilities of the current generation of

technologies, each aimed to fuel what must be a time-limited gold rush. What happens in our applications when the bubble bursts?²⁷

- VI. Implicated in all of this is a further area of ethical peril: as in blue collar occupations in the past, automation runs the risk of creating technological unemployment, this time in the heritage sector. In *Congruence Engine* our ethos has been that these techniques could enable data-creation effort (read, ‘cataloguing’) that heritage organisations have rarely been able to afford. Ideally, part-mechanising this activity will eventually lead to displacement of curatorial work into more social roles related to using collections more creatively. But the record of historical precedent in relation to technological unemployment is mixed and transitions are often painful.²⁸

All this points to the need to develop well informed and critical ethics on a deliberative model (not just the issuing of guidelines) to guide the sector through the likely stormy next few years. With regard to the use of LLMs, it indicates the avoidance of trivial use, the investigation – and perhaps development of – open-source LLMs,²⁹ and the championing of ‘minimal computing’ solutions.³⁰ The sector will need to balance the costs of machine-learning solutions with the costs and benefits of choosing lower-tech, more labour-intensive, approaches.

As historians of science and technology we are conscious too that, reporting now at such a point of flux, we are also witnesses to a kind of technological change that we would at other times be analysing historically, and that the technical possibilities that we are able to articulate now will soon become part of the historical evidence for our period.

Next Steps, as they seem to us

We can envisage a world of linked and open heritage data, in which not only is it easy to find related items across collections, but where any collections item – object, picture, archive document, film, historic building record – can be seen within a ‘data neighbourhood’, to use another of our project metaphors, a virtual reconstruction of the social-historical stratum from which it was removed at the point of acquisition. We can even imagine that world of linked and open data as covering all subject matter and all collections. But such a world is a distant prospect; as Alex Butterworth put it in our project manifesto:

Congruence Engine prototypes a framework for the creation of a national datascape of cultural heritage as an act of cathedral building: generational in its trajectory.³¹

Before we can reach up to that vision, we will need to do more research to create tools and gain wisdom about ethical practice, in parallel with demonstrating the potential of collections linkage at scale by creating prototypes for future infrastructure:

- Tools and interfaces: a crucial area of research and development that we need. Most of the techniques we have developed have required convoluted pipelines and hand-coding using very new computing techniques that have been evolving fast. We need to equip the social machine of people who will link collections with apps and user interfaces so that everyday practitioners can readily create data from complex sources for their own purposes, and archive the resulting datasets in a sustainable manner.
- We need a programme of deliberative ethics with wide participation from organisations and individuals to work through the dangers and appetites for applying machine learning to heritage data.

- To move beyond proof-of-concept, we need to create scalable prototypes for future infrastructure: these will be diverse in subject, collections type and location. Amongst participants are likely to be: NMDC museums, IROs, local authority GLAMs, the Museum Data Service, suppliers of collections management systems and Wikimedia UK.

10. Project Outputs

Exhibits

We produced two exhibits of differing styles. From October 2023 to February 2024, we presented a small installation at the Discovery Museum, Newcastle (one of our collaborating organisations). This consisted of four short films (each around 90 seconds in duration), selectable by visitors: the first an introduction to the project’s aims, with the other three each showcasing one of our investigations (3D reconstruction, geolocating industry, and industrial folk songs). The whole was complemented by a selection of energy-related exhibits selected by the museum). The films are available [on the project website](#) and will be made available via the SMG repository after project end.

Figure 6: Congruence Engine exhibit at Discovery Museum, Newcastle, October 2023 - February 2024

The second, and much more substantial, exhibit, a map-based interactive giving access to substantial collections relating to the industrial history of Bradford, opened to the public at the Science and Media Museum in Bradford in early January 2025. Developed with Stamen, the Los Angeles based data visualisation design studio, this shows, for the Bradford region, the ways that collections could be explored in a world of linked open data. A wall-filling screen shows the map, and photographs, whilst a touch screen enables

visitors to explore not just local places and stories, but also the digital techniques we have used to extract and link them. The exhibit will run for at least half of Bradford City of Culture 2025.

Figure 7: 'The Connection Engine' final *Congruence Engine* interactive exhibit at the Science and Media Museum, Bradford

Project Film

Bradford Forwards and Backwards is a 25-minute film inspired by the project. Made by Common Films, who also created the films for the Newcastle exhibit, it shares the earlier films' approach of 'showing not telling' the concerns of the project. It links historic mill sites in the city with the work of the Bradford Heritage Recording Unit, both the photographs and the oral histories, reflecting on the shift to a post-industrial era, and on the nature of memory and historical record. It will show at selected film festivals in 2025 before being made generally available via the Science Museum's British Library-hosted Research Repository.

The **Project Blog** has so far featured:

- *We are Congruence Engine: Metaphors and Project Conduct* (22 Feb 2022)
- *Methods: Seeking congruence and enabling divergence* (14 March 2022)
- *The Congruence Engine opening conference – enacting the principles of systemic action research* (24 March 2022)
- *Congruence Engine North Star* (24 March 2022)
- *Energising materials, connecting stories – local, national and international* (25 May 2022)

- What can Omeka do for your digital journey? Reflections from the first *Congruence Engine* Pilot Study (1 Jul 2022)
- Co-producing research inquiries for the textiles strand (2 Aug 2022)
- Reflecting on the Textiles Pilot (22 Aug 2022)
- Trying out Gale Digital Scholar Lab (18 Oct 2022)
- Giving voice to hidden collections: Insights from the oral history investigation (27 Oct 2022)
- Occupations, Machines, People: The connective tissue that helps us connect collections (11 Jan 2023)
- Directory Enquiries: Machine learning to unlock radical historical context, part one (6 Feb 2023)
- National Collection as Social Machine: Modelling through Action Research (16 May 2023)
- Data is never raw: Ethics and biases in digital cultural heritage collections (20 June 2023)
- Let's digitally reassemble industrial heritage collections (23 June 2023)
- Reanimating the past? You've got a NERF! (25 October 2023)
- Zoom into the past: Mapping across scale (25 October 2023)
- Let the history speak and sing: Unlocking the living, human and experiential knowledge of folk songs and oral histories (25 October 2023)
- *Congruence Engine* in Bradford: Towards a local instance of the National Collection as Social Machine (19 December 2023)
- Weaving the Strands: Modelling the *Congruence Engine* (December 2024)

Reports

Shoab Sufi, Emily Bell, & Anna-Maria Sichani. (2023). *Report on the AHRC Digital/ Software Requirements Survey 2021: Where is Investment Needed? (1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7686348>

Hawkins, Ashleigh, and Anna Maria Sichani, 'Data Matters': *Report on the Towards a National Collection Discovery Projects Focus Group on Data Management, Documentation, and Archiving Practices in Digital Cultural Heritage Projects* (Towards a National Collection, 29 October 2024), doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14006955>

Magazine Publications

Rees, Arran. opinion piece, *Museums Journal* (Museum Association Magazine), Jan/Feb 2022, pp 12., <https://www.museumsassociation.org/museums-journal/opinion/2022/01/digital-the-potential-of-ai/>

Boon, Tim. "The Congruence Engine." *Viewpoint* (BSHS Magazine), no. 126, Feb. 2022, pp. 8–9. <https://www.bshs.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/No-126-Feb-2022-for-web.pdf>

Congruence Engine special issue of the Science Museum Group Journal

A double-sized special issue of the *Science Museum Group Journal* showcasing the *Congruence Engine* project was published a year into the project. This edition contains 18 papers featuring experimental and new forms of writing that include scene-setting pieces, collaborative authorship, and single-author essays with writers contributing their individual skill and perspective, and other pieces which explore what it means to come together within the project. [Autumn 2022 - Science Museum Group Journal](#)

The published issue contains the following articles:

Author	Article	Article type/subject/origin
Introduction/Editorial		
Tim Boon	Origins and Ambitions of the <i>Congruence Engine</i> Project	Single author article
Helen Graham, Arran Rees	<i>Congruence Engine</i> in action	Editorial
Alex Butterworth	The <i>Congruence Engine</i> Manifesto	Single author article
Research papers		
Will Ashworth	History of textiles and the <i>Congruence Engine</i>	Single author article
Paul Craddock	Connecting with industrial heritage and collections using video production methods	Short video and film essay
Tim Smith	Textiles in the modern age	Photo essay
John Stack, Jamie Unwin	The potential and pitfalls of machine learning in the <i>Congruence Engine</i> context	Two-author article
Graeme Gooday, Kylea Little, Bernard Musesengwe, Cameron Tailford	Energising connections in museum collections	Multi-author article
Asa Calow	The future: reflections on emerging machine learning methods for digital heritage	Single author article
Discussion papers/Conversations		
Arran Rees, Anna-Maria Sichani and Stefania Zardini Lacedelli	Surfacing multiple perspectives on keywords for the <i>Congruence Engine</i> ; embracing multiplicity, interdisciplinarity, and mutual learning	Conversation
Kylea Little, Ellie Swinbank, Felicity McWilliams	'South Kensington is practically as far away as Munich': the making of Industrial Collections in Edinburgh, Newcastle and Birmingham	Discussion paper
Ben Russell and Wayne Cocroft	Connecting places and collections	Two-author hybrid: discussion / photo essay
Jon Agar	History of communications and the <i>Congruence Engine</i> : early thoughts and possibilities	Single author article
Daniel C S Wilson	Working at scale: what do computational methods mean for research using cases, models and collections?	Single author article
Simon Popple and Stefania Zardini Lacedelli, Arran J Rees, Stuart Prior, and Maggie Smith	Collaborative conversation as a method for exploring multiple perspectives on 'community' and forms of knowledge in the <i>Congruence Engine</i>	Conversation piece
Jane Winters and Anna-Maria Sichani	The role of digital humanities in an interdisciplinary research project	Two-author article
Review		
Lauren Ryall-White	<i>Living with Machines</i>	
Obituary		
Tim Boon and Graeme Gooday	Cameron James Tailford (Research Fellow), 10 October 1991 – 3 August 2022	

Project Books

1. Emergent Histories: New Work in the Digital History of Industry and Collections from the *Congruence Engine* Project

This substantial 160,000-word book of 18 chapters, to be published early in 2026 by UCL Press, reports on the project’s philosophy, course, investigations and findings. After a substantial introduction, its three sections cover foundations (project history, approach to race and decolonisation, and history of collections and data); themes (historical narratives produced using the project’s digital techniques); and the digital techniques the team has explored.

Emergent Histories: New Work in the Digital History of Industry and Collections from the <i>Congruence Engine</i> Project	
Key: LA = lead author; MC = major contributor; C = contributor	
Tim Boon	Introduction
A. FOUNDATIONS	
Arran Rees (LA), Tim Boon (MC)	‘We Are <i>Congruence Engine</i> ’: A History of the Project
Katerina Webb-Bourne (LA), Arran Rees, Julia Ankenbrand (MCs) Helen Graham, Alex Fitzpatrick (Cs)	[title tbc] The Project is Very White: Experiments in Resisting Inclusion and Diversity Paradigms
Ben Russell (LA), Tim Boon (MC), Jayne Knight (C)	The Mind of the Curator?: On the cataloguing language of technical museum collections
Bernard Musesengwe (LA), Daniel Belteki (MC), Tim Boon (C)	Discovery Museum and Science Museum: Historical Connections Through Museum Collection
B. THEMES	
Graeme Gooday (LA), Bernard Musesengwe, Daniel Belteki (MCs), Kylea Little (C)	Connecting Energy Collections: New Stories from Digital Tools
Stefania Zardini Lacedelli (LA), Alex Butterworth, Stef De Sabbata (MCs)	A New Age for Sonic History: empowering audio heritage to illuminate The Human Dimension of the Industrial Past
Max Long (LA), Natasha Kitcher, Daniel Belteki (MCs), Robert Hellawell (C)	Towards a Natural Collection: Digital and Community Histories of River Pollution in Bradford
Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi (LA), Alex Butterworth (MC), Jo Kent (MC), Colin Coates (C)	A Village through Time: Mapping Genealogies, Occupations and Social Mobility in Saltaire
C. TECHNIQUES	
Natasha Kitcher (LA), Daniel Belteki, Max Long, Anna-Maria Sichani (MCs), Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi, Felix Needham-Simpson (c)	Before You Begin: Processing and Transcribing Historic Data using Digital Methods
Formerly: Andrew Richardson (LA), Alex Butterworth (MC), Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi (C)	Flow States: Novel Approaches for Visualisation of Graphed Industrial History and Heritage

Yichang Sun (LA), Alex Butterworth (MC), Sam Griffiths (MC)	Trade-Directory Data, Space Syntax and the Multi-Scalar Constitution of 19thC Bradford
Sarah Middle (LA), Alex Butterworth (MC), Arran Rees (Cs) AND Nayomi Kasthuri (C) Arachchi (LA)	An Ontological Approach to Occupations: Modelling Work in and around the Textile Industry
Jon Agar (LA), Natasha Kitcher, Asa Calow (MC), Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi (C)	Generative AI Today: Using GPT for Historical Work
Natasha Kitcher (LA), Geoff Belknap, Daniel Belteki (MC), Kunika Kono, Kaspar Beelen (C)	Computer Vision Questions: What Linkage Through Visual Terms Empowers Historians and Curators to Consider
Daniel Belteki (LA), Max Long, Natasha Kitcher (MCs), Patrick Russell, Tim Boon, Kaspar Beelen, Stephen McConnachie (Cs)	Film and Computer Vision
Alex Fitzpatrick (LA), Natasha Kitcher, Geoff Belknap (MCs), Max Long, Daniel Belteki (Cs)	Exploring the Value of Crowdsourcing to Enhance Collections in the Age of AI
Tim Boon (LA), Ben Russell, Max Long (MCs), Felix Needham-Simpson (C)	Creating a Textile Machinery Nomenclature Link via Wikidata
Max Long (LA), Tim Boon (MC), Stephen Weldon (C)	Building an Object-Enriched Bibliography: Experiments in Linking Museum Objects and Academic Literature

2. The UK Digital Collection: A Manifesto (working title)

This short 30,000-word book substantially written by *Congruence Engine's* core investigator team is expected to be published early in 2026 by the University of London Press. It will use the Manifold platform for the online version enabling linkage to online assets, reading group activities etc. It is intended to make the case for the *Congruence Engine* approach to collections linkage. It will outline our philosophy; the need for collections linkage that arises alike from lay and professional engagement in history / heritage and the existence and underuse of collections; the political theory that situates the model; what will need to happen; and how it may change practice in history, digital humanities and museums.

The UK Digital Collection: A Manifesto (working title)	
Alex Butterworth, lead author (LA)	Chapter 1: Introduction to <i>Congruence Engine</i> and the Social Machine Metaphor
Tim Boon (LA)	Chapter 2: Collections, Documentation and Public History
Helen Graham (LA)	Chapter 3: Decentralisation and Commons: Context for Social Machines
Arran Rees (LA)	Chapter 4: The Social Machine in Practice: Socio-Technical Insights
Jane Winters (LA)	Chapter 5: Implications for Research Practices

11. Cross-Project Collaboration

Apart from the two reports listed in 10 above, there were other kinds of collaboration as the Discovery Projects learned from the Foundation Projects (in our case directly as we absorbed and developed the insights from *Heritage Connector* in addition to learning from several others, especially *Locating a National Collection*). We were also in dialogue with the SPF1 project *Living with Machines*, with whom we shared historical interests and one staff member. But cross-Discovery Project collaboration proved difficult. Because the AHRC funded the five Discovery Projects as conventional research projects (with separate aims, objectives and research questions) the scheme lacked the inbuilt mechanisms to compel collaboration, and the separate delivery timetables meant that attempts at collaboration – which *Congruence Engine* promoted on several occasions – proved impossible to fulfil. There were commonalities of technique and concerns (as well as differing areas of focus) and so synthesis is possible, and we strongly encourage this to be undertaken as a next stage in the ambitions for the work that needs to be done.

12. Infrastructure, Data Management and Sustainability

As members of an interdisciplinary and collaborative project, the *Congruence Engine* team have developed and refined a dynamic, accessible and sustainable technical infrastructure both for communicating within the team and for storing, documenting, sharing and preserving data, code and other outputs.

Open, Responsible and Reproducible Research

The project team developed and shared a commitment to open, responsible and reproducible research, and made it an embedded project practice and guiding principle throughout. This approach was applied to choices and decision-making: from data management and documentation to communication channels, infrastructure choices and sustainability planning. In the context of our data-centred digital cultural heritage work, responsible research refers not only to the identification and treatment of ethical, legal and social aspects of cultural heritage data but also to an integrated and iterative set of principles and processes that support and promote the values of transparency, equity and care while we interact with cultural heritage data, digital tools and methods, data subjects and other stakeholders.

Minimal Infrastructure

From the outset, the *Congruence Engine* team worked to develop precise research questions iteratively through the collaborative processes adopted for individual investigations, rather than starting with a preset definition of infrastructure. Team members explored-by-doing a ‘minimal infrastructure’ approach where possible, aiming to reduce barriers to access and engagement with computational tools and processes but also to address the environmental impacts of our computation.

A key project principle was that our infrastructure choices and decisions should be pragmatic, using pre-existing tools and software rather than building bespoke solutions, and particularly having in mind the sustainability of systems and outputs beyond the grant period of the project. Consequently, instead of setting up a fully-fledged infrastructure with predefined frameworks and fixed specifications, including data storage, containers and development environments, we invested in a distributed, flexible infrastructure by establishing a set of core components for data-derived outputs and computational work, including the Box storage space, a [project-owned GitHub repository](#), and investigation into the practicalities of an institutionally-hosted Virtual Machine. From this baseline, each investigation team was able to customise their own working and development environment by choosing from existing services and tools. In addition to this, team members were encouraged to set up and use their own collaborative development spaces, such as Jupyter notebooks or GoogleCollab, and to develop workflows that enabled them to perform and collaborate more effectively by respecting individual technical and programming expertise and communication preferences.

Communication Infrastructure

Aligned with the project’s action research methodology, we recognised the critical role of communication and documentation platforms, especially given the hybrid nature of the project. To support flexible and iterative collaboration, a communication infrastructure was established to accommodate the geographically dispersed interdisciplinary team most often working remotely and asynchronously. Initially, we used Basecamp for open

discussions, sharing, and announcements. In January 2023, we started using [Notion](#) to enhance documentation, knowledge development, and collaborative reflection. With its cross-platform availability and third-party integrations, Notion was instrumental in promoting transparency, documenting meetings, encouraging the writing of reflective work diaries, and fostering a sense of shared development. To address the challenges of tracking progress across parallel workstreams and highlighting interdependencies, a sub-group gradually introduced the use of Slack from October 2023 as an additional communication channel. Our multi-platform approach reflects the project's iterative and experimental nature; it accommodated varying levels of engagement – from official updates via Basecamp to open documentation in Notion and dynamic day-to-day conversations on Slack.

Data Ingestion, Archiving and Storage

The *Congruence Engine* project team, in common with other Discovery projects, has been at the forefront of addressing issues related to documentation, processing, archiving, and the publication of data-derived outputs within the digital cultural heritage landscape. Representatives of the team explored these issues at a cross-TaNC level and contributed to a collaborative report.³²

The project collected diverse cultural heritage datasets from its partners through various ingestion methods. Once gathered, these datasets, along with others created during the project, were used for its investigations. Managing these datasets required customised solutions to ensure their secure storage, proper curation, thorough documentation, appropriate access status, and sustainable maintenance.

The project had to balance priorities, needs and resources to make decisions regarding short- and long-term storage and archiving solutions for its datasets (both ingested and developed ones) and data-derived outputs. A mixed approach was adopted, using commercial solutions for day-to-day, short-term data storage, sharing and access (Box, MicrosoftSuite) and institutionally enabled, open solutions for more permanent archiving needs ([GitHub](#), [SMG open institutional repository](#), [Zenodo](#)). The specific copyright and licensing conditions, along with the digital systems policies of certain datasets, posed challenges for the ingestion and reuse of partners' datasets, especially for experimental AI-enabled processes, and this necessitates careful case-by-case evaluation.

Data Documentation

The *Congruence Engine* project developed a distributed, multi-layered approach to data documentation using different practices and systems to store information at multiple points in the data flow, including: basic text (ReadMe.md or .txt) files at ingestion stage; a datasets database for management purposes; datasheets for datasets at investigation level to capture more detailed information regarding the creation, provenance and (re)use of datasets; and finally a [CE Data Register](#), powered by Wikibase, as a proof-of-concept to experiment with semantically enabled linkage of datasets.

Data Sharing, Legacy and Sustainability

As part of *Congruence Engine's* commitment to responsible research, CE investigations and their diverse outputs were developed, maintained, published, and disseminated with an emphasis on openness (as far as possible), reproducibility, transparency and thorough documentation.

To support this, our dedicated [GitHub repository](#) was created, with each substantial investigation having a dedicated space to host a variety of data derived outputs, including: 1) datasets provided by project partners (as permitted) or

generated by the project team; 2) code, models, and software, either customised or originally developed by the team; 3) documentation for datasets (Datasheets); and 4) other outputs such as toolkits, prototypes, or designs. Additionally, GitHub Pages were deployed from these repositories to enhance the visibility, reproducibility, and long-term maintenance of the investigation outputs, contributing to the project’s legacy.

Congruence Engine has also embraced a responsible approach to credit attribution by employing the [CRediT Taxonomy](#) for its final publications.

Figure 8: *Congruence Engine*’s GitHub landing page

Training as Infrastructure

In *Congruence Engine*, an interdisciplinary project, levels of digital expertise varied significantly across the team, creating challenges of (un)familiarity with the infrastructure and technical choices, as well as towards the sustainability of the project’s outputs. From the outset, the project focused on human aspects of infrastructure: questions of training, and consequent impact on the choices made by teams regarding programming options, interfaces, and software used. We sought to overcome these barriers by promoting a ‘training-as-infrastructure approach’ across the highly interdisciplinary team through a variety of training and mutual learning sessions, digital drop-in sessions, reading groups and meeting spaces. We developed a three-tier training programme, which balanced the acquisition of generic core skills with more specific needs arising directly from the practical experience of the project. Fortnightly drop-in sessions enabled researchers

to talk through their data and research questions on an informal basis with data scientists (and vice versa). These sessions also helped to surface immediate training needs that arose from investigations, and these could be followed up relatively rapidly with bespoke provision on an individual or small-group basis. Finally, a [more structured general training programme](#) introduced key digital tools and concepts, for example the use of GitHub or the broad concepts of linked open data and machine learning for cultural heritage.

Training

This space is used to create and maintain training material developed as part of the Congruence Engine project. All materials listed and developed are to be used under CC-BY-SA licences.

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Round 1 (autumn 2022) - Data cleaning and structuring

Round 2 (spring 2023) - Version Control, Linked Open Data and Machine Learning

Round 3 (autumn 2023) - GenAI for cultural heritage

Round 2 (spring 2024) - AI methods and ethics for Cultural Heritage

Please contact annamaria.sichani@sas.ac.uk for more information on training and mutual learning opportunities within The Congruence Engine Project.

Figure 9: The publicly available GitHub repository of the CE training programme and materials

13. Final Recommendations

Summary Recommendations

What

The 'UK digital collection' should be understood in practice to be a facilitative infrastructure for collections linkage ('UK collections linkage'), not a standalone digital collection.

How (by what means)

- **Accessible Technical Infrastructure:** We recommend the creation and maintenance of an accessible, open, technical infrastructure to enable participatory collections linkage using Linked Open Data (LOD) principles and via open data repositories.
- **Heritage organisation datafication** of collections to enable this linkage.
- **People and skills:** We recommend long-term government investment to ensure the continuity of digital, historical, curatorial, and hybrid skills in the GLAM sector.

How (in what manner)

- **Social Machine:** All stakeholders should accept that, although automation using digital technique is essential, it will be human motivation and action – both individual and institutional – that determines which collections and historical data are made linkable, and are linked.
- **Anti-Oppressive Practice:** UK collections linkage should embrace anti-oppressive practice as a guiding principle to mitigate perpetuation of harm, especially as encoded in GLAM collections data.
- **Open Access Data:** Data deriving from public sources should be created and retained, openly accessible in public repositories, without commercial paywalls, however its creation is funded.

Who

- **Diversity of Action:** We recommend that the creation of this infrastructure be undertaken by means of the enrolment of diverse heritage organisations, communities and people to create, curate and link collections and their data.
- **Leadership** should come from a coalition of senior figures in the heritage sector (perhaps led by NMDC), DCMS and UKRI, with IROC providing expertise.
- **Funding:** The research, digitisation/datafication and long-term implementation phases to this work each require bespoke funding from appropriate sources: UKRI, DCMS, MHLG, NHLF, trusts and foundations.

Full Recommendations

UK collections linkage has both social and digital components. It will rely strongly on people and the **care** they have for heritage, their **contributions** to making and maintaining heritage, and the **connections** forged through that work.

The collections to be linked are heterogenous in ownership (from national GLAMs via local authority to private museums, and private collections), scale (from millions of items to dozens) and medium (objects, documents, publications, records, visual and time-based media and records of historical places).

Building UK collections linkage is a substantial undertaking. In *Congruence Engine* we have been exploring, via the social machine metaphor, how this can be accomplished. Paying particular attention to how the social and technical might be combined, our recommendations for developing a united digital collection are as follows:

What

The ‘UK digital collection’ should be understood in practice to be a facilitative infrastructure for collections linkage (‘UK collections linkage’), not a standalone digital collection.

Following the TaNC mandate, our principal focus has been the liberation of large publicly owned collections, but the principles that apply there also apply across the whole ecosystem of heritage, stretching to the individual collector.

- The priority of heritage organisations, especially those that have invested in new storage for their reserve collections, is to make their physical collections intellectually accessible. Pooling data will be attractive to them insofar as it enhances the visibility and usability of their collections and enables them to conduct their core functions more effectively.
- GLAM custody of collections imposes the obligation of very long term record keeping, meaning that their interest is also in holding the primary digital record – however enriched – of the items in their care. Ready access to this data or either directly from the institutions, or through open distributed repositories via APIs, rather than wholesale duplication in a UK digital collection, should provide the way forward.

How (by what means)

The creation of UK collections linkage requires four categories of activity in overlapping phases:

- Continuing research: to create the needed scalable prototypes for a future infrastructure (large scale proof-of-concept, building on TaNC), the (digital) apps and user interfaces, and debate on the (ethical) frameworks to enable this. This may best continue on a project basis.
- Digitisation and datafication of collections to enable their linkage (rolling-out the necessary transformations and techniques across the GLAM sector). This should be enacted on a programme – not project – basis at the decade-length scale.
- Creation and ready availability of social historical datasets (‘connective tissue data’) for linkage, hosted in open repositories.

- Long-term implementation of linkage by a wide variety of organisations and people supported by techniques and frameworks developed in i, acting on data produced in ii and iii.

Accessible Technical Infrastructure: We recommend the creation and maintenance of an accessible, open, technical infrastructure to enable participatory collections linkage using Linked Open Data (LOD) principles and via open data repositories.

To be sustainable and useful, UK collections linkage must be accessible to everyone. We recommend:

- the creation and maintenance of simple, scalable, accessible, and open technical infrastructure – including a data registry and a resource index (for ontologies, thesauruses, gazetteers etc) – to enable participatory collections linkage.
- investment in resources, systems and services to enable more diverse engagement and contributions.

Data Infrastructure: UK collections linkage must be supported by a shared and open data infrastructure that organisations and individuals are able easily to access.

We recommend:

- Collections data should be transformed to adhere to shared standards and principles such as IIF and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), learning from initiatives like OpenGLAM and Collections as Data.³³
- Collections data should be published with licences that allow for further enhancements and its use as Linked Open Data on the model of, or using, shared and open platforms such as Wikidata and FreeCen.³⁴
- The GLAM digital backlog should be addressed by supporting programmes that produce machine-readable and interoperable data, though not necessarily full-scale cataloguing (as linked open data may reduce the need for this).
- A long-term funding strategy to avoid the privatisation of key public data assets and infrastructure.
- Long term funding for the Museum Data Service and similar services for the library and archive sector (potentially an aspect of the UK National Data Library)
- Provision of funding and technical support to GLAM organisations lacking specialist digital departments for the preparation of collections data.

Heritage organisations and other collection-holders should move to datify their collections to enable this linkage. For each organisation, this will require:

- Thoughtful and careful selection of levels of record and other material to datify. In the world of LOD, all data has value because it enhances linkage. Organisations will benefit from extending their item records by adding associated material from older catalogues, exhibition text, support files, etc.
- Extraction of terminology using Named Entity Recognition, Regular Expressions, OpenRefine and other programs, preparing data for later entity linkage.
- Selective catalogue enhancement, most likely with the help of human-overseen digital techniques, tightening of dates and identification of the associations and purposes of collections items.

People and skills: We recommend long-term investment to ensure the continuity of digital, historical, curatorial, and hybrid skills in the GLAM sector.

We recommend:

- UKRI, DCMS, MHLG and other major funders should support the development of career paths for long-term digital and hybrid roles in GLAM organisations.
- The provision of long-term or permanent roles for heritage data scientists within GLAM organisation to sustain and embed open collections data usage.
- Development of programmes to improve digital literacy and skills in smaller organisations and community groups to reduce barriers to contribution.
- Involvement of local heritage practitioners and small heritage organisations in paid capacities and with training programmes available.
- Employment of facilitators to build relationships, surface and negotiate knowledge systems and power structures, and support the (un)learning necessary to collaboratively build anti-oppressive collections-linking work.
- The salary discrepancy between the GLAM and private sector – especially with regard to the employment of people with data skills – be addressed and mitigated by offering stability, good work environments and interesting collaborative work to foster innovation and growth.

With regard to research projects:

- UKRI should issue further guidance on productive and realistic FTE time commitments for investigators.
- UKRI should require that larger projects are resourced with project managers, coordinators, and administrators for working across organisations.
- UKRI should consider organising future research programmes that have a common aim in such a way that expectations of cross-project collaboration are built-in and actionable.

How (in what manner)

Social Machine: All stakeholders should accept that, although automation using digital technique is essential, it will be human motivation and action – both individual and institutional – that determines which collections and historical data are made linkable, and are linked.

Congruence Engine has shared the experience of other practitioners in this field: that data creation, curation and linkage is an intensely human activity.³⁵

We recommend:

- The promotion of social capital through an emphasis on the role of people within and beyond collection-holding heritage organisations.
- The coalition responsible for developing UK collections linkage should issue clear guidance on both social and technical infrastructural resources.
- A programme of deliberative ethics should explore the moral hazards of working with large language models and collections data guidelines, including environmental impacts, and potential technological unemployment, and their mitigation (see report section 9)

Anti-oppressive Practice

UK collections linkage should encompass the breadth of UK cultural heritage and everyone it can speak to. It should therefore embrace anti-oppressive practice as a core guiding principle.

We recommend:

- Addressing gaps and biases (otherwise ‘positionality’) in cultural heritage collections data and embedding details of origin within the collections metadata
- Discussion of racism, whiteness, and intersectionality should be integrated into the working practices of all contributors to linkage.
- Understanding and addressing unequal power structures within the heritage sector that may cause holders of smaller collections and partners to reject involvement in UK collections linkage.
- Government and its departments and agencies to direct investment towards resources and infrastructure in traditionally underrepresented or underserved institutions and communities using models that work for those communities.

Open Access Data

Data deriving from public sources should be created and retained openly accessible in public repositories, without commercial paywalls, however its creation is funded. (The terms under which, for example, both historical newspaper corpora and the Census have been privatised by collaboration with the private sector has both placed this public data behind paywalls and, significantly for our enterprise, removed it from the full interoperability that will be necessary for effective collections linkage.)

Who

People power the social machine; investment in people and skills is vital to the success of UK collections linkage. Instability of roles and insufficient resourcing militate against this. We recommend:

- **Diversity of Action:** We recommend that the creation of this infrastructure should enrol diverse heritage organisations, communities and people in creating, curating and linking collections and their data.
- **Leadership** should come from a coalition of senior figures in the heritage sector (perhaps led by NMDC), DCMS and UKRI, with IROC providing expertise.
- **Funders:** The three overlapping phases of this work (research, digitisation/datafication and long-term implementation) each require bespoke funding from appropriate sources: UKRI, DCMS (local authorities), NHLF, trusts and foundations.

14. Contacts

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15. Annex: List of Investigations

Our intention, from the time of the application onwards, was to attune a set of digital collections-linking techniques to the answering of real life historical and curatorial enquiries. In the project we modelled this through separate and associated investigations that used a wide variety of digital techniques to create data from analogue sources with the aim thereby of linking collections. Some investigations also created visualisations and prototype user interfaces to enable this work. Occurring when it did, the project was able to experiment widely with newly available Large Language Model technologies, including generative AIs, in a way that we could not have anticipated.

Modelling the action of a future social machine for collections linkage, most of these investigations were motivated by the historical interests of researchers and other participants, with some being commissioned or more directed from the centre. They all entailed differing combinations of digital and historical work, but within an assumption that digital techniques should always be an important aspect.

Some of the investigations were directly about linkage between collections, and others were at one step removed, ordering and using historical data – our ‘connective tissue data’ – that will be needed to incorporate collections items within complex, data-informed, social histories.

Various working definitions of our core ‘social machine’ metaphor were at play during the investigations. The whole team embraced it as a way of paying attention to the complex interactions between the capacity of programs to automate certain data manipulation activities, and the necessary human interventions – to stimulate and to correct, classify and approve. But this metaphor also allowed for more tightly defined interpretations, especially in relation to the use of social historical data (in our case taking the Bradford example), its ordering and relationships. This can be seen in the linked investigations numbered 23-28 below, along with the ultimate potential to orchestrate data-related social processes using bespoke graphical user interfaces as outlined in 33.

Note on work with Wikimedia UK: Wikipedia and Wikidata

Throughout *Congruence Engine*, with Wikimedia as a partner (and following the involvement of Wikidata in our Foundation Project *Heritage Connector*), the question of the role of the Wikimedia Foundation umbrella in collections linkage was recurrent. Several investigations investigated it, some in passing. These ranged from a close interrogation of the extent to which ChatGPT responses to user questions echoed Wikipedia entries, through to the experimental use of ‘blinkage’ of entities to Wikidata Q-codes – as identified by SpaCY – in the ‘Mining Review’ newsreel and in the oral histories processed alongside. The ‘congruent data tool’ included a facility to enable candidate linkage of this kind and its inspection and validation by non-expert users. The Wikidata approach was most actively pursued in investigation 10 (creating a textile machinery nomenclature).

Collections (and how to link them)

1. The role of Science Museum objects in the founding of the Museum of Science and Industry, Newcastle – Daniel Belteki, Bernard Musesengwe

Aims: To use the example of known historical transfers of specific objects between museums to test the capabilities of digital techniques to aid understanding of the diaspora of objects between collections.

Conduct: The investigation examined the founding of the Museum of Science and Industry in Newcastle (the predecessor of the Discovery Museum) through the histories of the objects that were transferred from the Science Museum to Newcastle in the early 1930s. The investigation identified around 300 relevant objects and revealed historic descriptions of 37 objects from historic Science Museum catalogues.

Results: The investigation demonstrated that provenance work is not amenable to machine techniques and must rely on detailed archive research by humans. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

2. Mind of the Curator – *Tim Boon, Ben Russell, Felix Needham-Simpson, Jayne Knight*

Aims: To develop understanding of how past curatorial practice inflects the data that the Science Museum holds on its objects.

Conduct: An investigation with both archival research and digital components, taking the example of the Science Museum’s 1921 published catalogue of its textile machinery collection. We explored the nature of the – highly technical – language, using Surprisingly Frequent Phrase Detection and KeyBERT techniques to analyse and visualise this (via Voyant Tools). We contextualised this via new archival research into the curatorial working culture of the interwar Science Museum and via a comparison with the 1970s+ practice of the Bradford Industrial Museum. We hypothesised a way to understand the language via Ludwick Fleck’s notion of ‘thought collective’.

Results: The investigation provided strong empirical evidence for understanding why our collections-related data takes the form it does. It also led to the Wikidata Taxonomy project (10 below). A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/mind-of-the-curator>

3. Museums' online catalogue-as-data – *Anna-Maria Sichani, Jamie Unwin*

Aims: To assess online museum catalogues-as-data, by exploring and demystifying common practices in museum online catalogues, aiming to reveal potential obstacles that suspend their connectivity and advanced use from various users.

Conduct: We conducted an analysis of the state-of-the-art of digital cataloguing practices in the museum sector. Following this, we focused on specific technical challenges, found in online museum catalogues, by introducing a sector-specific assessment framework through a combination of empirical research and landscape analysis. For this framework we employed the Science Museum Group (SMG) online collection catalogue as a case study to showcase existing challenges and limitations. Finally, we proposed a minimum technical passive provision to serve as a foundational infrastructure for drawing together a cultural heritage national collection.

Results: As part of this investigation we produced a report alongside an assessment framework and matrix for museums’ online catalogues. This report aims to contribute towards the design and development of a sector-level strategy regarding the improvement and connectivity of online catalogues of cultural heritage institutions as part of a national collection’s infrastructure.

<https://congruence-engine.github.io/catalogues-as-data/>

4. Datafication and Cultural Heritage collections data infrastructures. Critical Perspectives on documentation, cataloguing and data-sharing in cultural heritage institutions – Arran Rees, Daniel Belteki, Anna-Maria Sichani

Aims: To assess the landscape for cultural heritage collections data infrastructure in the UK through an empirical and critical perspective.

Conduct: This investigation consisted of a two-fold empirical study (survey and interviews) on cultural heritage collections data infrastructure of UK cultural heritage institutions. Through this investigation we map the infrastructure that cultural heritage organisations use to record and manage their collections, exploring the range of systems being used, the levels of complexity or ease at which collections data can be accessed, and the challenges, requirements and opportunities existing cultural heritage collections data infrastructures pose for creative, innovative and impactful collections-as-data future work.

Results: A conference presentation (DPASSH2024) and a journal article (under review).

<https://congruence-engine.github.io/datafication-cultural-heritage-institutions/>

5. Heritage Weaver: linking collections using computer vision – Natasha Kitcher, Kaspar Beelen

Aim: To look at how computer vision tools could draw connections between collections, relying on the way the objects look rather than metadata. An initial experiment with linking using descriptions generated by LLAVA was unsuccessful, showing there was a need for a more sophisticated approach. The investigation then pivoted and relied on a collaboration with Kaspar Beelen, using multimodal embeddings.

Conduct: We used CLIP to create embeddings for over 20,000 communications, textiles, and energy objects from NMS and SMG's collections and then relied on manual annotation workshops with curators and researchers to assess the accuracy of links created. We found that it was possible to fine-tune the model using these annotations to improve the accuracy of connections made thereafter. Continued work in this vein could create bespoke linked collections to help individual researchers. We also trialled using the tool to identify collections images within moving image and historic photography, which was a success.

Results: It is possible to connect collections without a) dictating a taxonomy or b) relying exclusively on metadata that accompanies objects in the CMS. This approach relies on images of objects being available, which is a slightly limiting factor, but may make the case for more funding to be dedicated to this work in the future. While we created a linked database of objects, we also created a tool that allows users to search collections with images or textual data. The results from this work could help curators identify objects for display, share hazards information, and highlight gaps in their collections – while it could also ensure researchers think about using objects more seriously in their own research. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/heritage-weaver>

6. Building an Object-Enriched Bibliography: Experiments in Linking Museum Objects and Academic Literature – Max Long, Tim Boon, Stephen Weldon

Aim: To create meaningful links between academic literature and museum objects, using data from the database of the ISIS Cumulative Bibliography (ISIS CB).

Conduct: We explored a variety of different methods for linkage, focussing on the textiles strand of the CE project. This included creating embeddings from a sample of full-text academic articles that are included in the ISIS CB, as well as extracting named entities using the Named Entity Recognition (NER) model GLiNER, which could then be matched with museum collections. We also surveyed existing UIs which aim to link collections and academic literature, including the latest integration of JSTOR and ArtStor.

Results: We found that a combination of NER and embeddings proved an effective method of linking academic articles to museum collections. However, this was a fairly intensive pipeline which would be difficult to apply at scale for a resource like the ISIS CB. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/Object-Enriched-Bibliography/tree/main>

Technologies of Enhancement: Collections and Connective Data

7. The power of advertisements – Daniel Belteki, Kunika Kono

Aim: The investigation aimed to assess the ways in which computer vision tools can be used to identify domestic appliances in historic advertisements and to link them to objects in collections. We also hoped to aid study of gendered depictions in advertisements.

Conduct: The investigation trialled several digital approaches that incorporate computer vision tools within their methods: VGG, identification with pre-trained models, and LLaVA. It tested these approaches on the recently digitised *The Electrical Age* journal, provided to the project by the Institute of Engineering and Technology.

Results: The investigation showcased the strengths and limitations of the different approaches. It highlighted where the human-in-the-loop is essential to various approaches. It established that in their current state, the tools could not assist addressing the gender-historical questions. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/The-power-of-advertisements>

8. Transforming personal researcher notes into archival descriptions – Natasha Kitcher

Aim: See if human generated notes could be automatically processed into catalogue descriptions or tags to improve the searchability of an archive without as much work relying on individual archivists.

Conduct: 11 volunteers from the Telecommunications Heritage Group conducted research into files within the BT Archive and provided their notes. I trialled KeyBERT for summarising these notes into keywords, and then built a Custom GPT to automatically generate descriptions of a certain length using the input data. The GPT could handle typed and handwritten notes very well.

Results: 14 new catalogue descriptions were created and deemed good enough by both the researchers and the archive team. BT felt they would always need a human in the loop at the final stage, but that this case study showed there was potential for greater volunteer engagement with the collection in a way that usefully produced catalogue descriptions for them. A final recommendation was made that AI use should be recorded in the archive, which BT have now instigated. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/transforming-researcher-notes>

9. Fine-Tuning a Named Entity Recognition for Textile Machinery – Max Long, Arran Rees, Kaspar Beelen

Aim: The limitations of Named Entity Recognition (NER) for specific cultural heritage tasks has been recognised throughout this project. This investigation made use of the release of a new generation of ‘universal’ NER models to fine-tune a model that can identify instances of historic textile machinery accurately.

Conduct: This investigation used a combination of manually labelled data and synthetic data to fine-tune a NER model. In the course of the investigation, we refined our approach to labelling, data creation, and the applications of the fine-tuned model. While our example is focussed on a narrow task, our experience showed that a similar endeavour using dictionaries and thesauruses at scale could result in a much more productive use of NER for cultural heritage.

Results: As well as the finished textiles-specific NER model, we released training datasets with full documentation, as well as code and tutorials for others to develop similar models. These are freely available on GitHub and Huggingface.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/universal-ner-with-gliner>

10. Creating a Textile Machinery Nomenclature Via Wikidata – Tim Boon, Max Long, Ben Russell, Felix Needham-Simpson

Aim: We wanted to see whether Wikidata could be used as a thesaurus ‘spine’, holding a standard set of taxonomical terms that could be included within the collections management records of museums and other heritage collections, enabling the linking of associated, similar and identical objects across collections.

Conduct: This investigation splintered from the ‘mind of the curator’ work (2 above) once it became clear that the rich and specific language of the 1921 Textile Machinery Catalogue was unlikely to yield the degree of specificity sought in curatorial comparison between collections. Relying on the very consistent quality of the catalogue’s typesetting, Needham-Simpson used some of the same data and tools (RegEx and OpenRefine) to derive candidate object names from the headings to the catalogue entries. Expert validation by Russell, the Science Museum Mechanical Engineering curator, converted this into a validated terms list (now extended to include the small number of new terms required for post-1921 acquisitions) that was then auto-uploaded to Wikidata as a set of 97 terms by Long. The resulting object names and related Qcodes have been uploaded into the Museum’s ‘Mimsy’ content management system. Subsequent research by Long (9 above) has shown that the Gliner universal NER also shows promise for the extraction of sector-specific terms.

Results: We have proof of concept that semi-automatic extraction of descriptive terms can, via Wikidata, enable the linkage of related objects between collections. The broader usefulness of the technique would depend on a broader constituency of museums opting to include the terms in their object records. And, what applies to textile machinery is applicable to any collections subject area. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/experimenting-wikidata>

11. Saltaire Households and Genealogies (Saltaire Phase 2), Data Preprocessing – Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi, Alex Butterworth, Felix Needham Simpson

Aim: To preprocess the dataset of census records from Saltaire contributed to the project by project volunteer and Saltaire local history expert Colin Coates and to augment the data with additional information and configure it for modelling as a Neo4j graph (strand b) and for incorporation into a suite of browser-based visualisations (strand c).

Conduct: We used various Python libraries in addition to third party repositories and APIs to supplement the base data with information on the gender of individuals and to geocode addresses to allow addresses to be mapped. We also augmented the data with lookups of occupations to the Booth-Armstrong Industrial Classification that formed the basis of the Saltaire socio-economic mapping investigation (39 and 40 below). In addition, we experimented with few-shot prompting of LLMs to specify full sets of familial relationships between family members recorded in the census.

Results: An extensive census dataset of a model village that can be explored through techniques such as graphing or digital visualisation. We have also produced a set of programmatic routines for information augmentation of census data, one of which (specification of familial relationships) remains a work in progress. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/saltaire-household-genealogies-education>

12. Modelling the Bradford Thrum: A Meta-Investigation – Alex Butterworth, Felix Needham Simpson

Aim: The development of multiple datasets, many used in later linkage experiments, culminating in *Congruence Engine* Data Model (see 26). This is imagined as an essential foundation for a multidimensional modelling of the development of nineteenth century industrial Bradford within a global, national and local infrastructure, with particular references to flows of materials and exports; and in the hope of later creating a post-industrial ‘digital twin’ to interrogate the nature of industrial heritage in the lived experience of health, crime, pollution and community.

Conduct: The work included novel approaches to Trade Directory data extraction, and it occurred in parallel with, but independent from, work undertaken during the project’s Turing Institute workshop.³⁶ The intention is to inform the design of a large-scale process to achieve machine-readable datafication and linkage, with data modelling referenced to the project’s occupations ontology (see 23). The primary aim here was to surface, realistically, the myriad challenges to automation of such a process and to understand better how those without specialist technical expertise might undertake the necessary work of data improvement.

Results: The outputs of this work fed into several other investigations, including Entity-Relation Extraction (13), Worstedopolis (18), Worsted Engineering Expert (14), and Developing a *Congruence Engine* Data Model for Industrial Bradford (26). It also contributed to the original design of the proposed Data Register/Resource Index technical infrastructure aimed to provide a glanceable/explorable visual record of the availability of datasets; the links already created to other datasets (with detail concerning the extent, confidence/quality); and the data resources (ontologies, vocabularies, gazetteers, etc) to which the linkage could be aligned or indexed. The ‘Bradford Thrum’ data is likely to form the basis of a future research funding application.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/trade-directories-data-extraction>

13. Entity-Relationship Extraction – Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi, Alex Butterworth, Felix Needham-Simpson

Aims: To develop a computational methodology for extracting and linking terms of interest from digitised historical datasets with a view to constructing a knowledge graph of linked terms from the extractions.

Conduct: The first round focussed on extracting terms related to occupations contained in digitised trade directories from Bradford and its environs, Directories of Archives and other sources, as well as the Dictionary of Occupational Terms compiled from the 1921 census. Our latter approach was based on employing a few-shot LLM prompting strategy both to extract terms of interest e.g. occupations as well as using generative AI to suggest the action that a person employed in the extracted occupation may have performed as well as the object(s) on which such an action would have been performed. Few-shot LLM prompting was a complementary approach to the problem in addition to the regex and NER techniques that had been tried earlier in the project.

Results: A set of routines for applying few-shot prompting for structured data extraction that can be applied to a wide range of CSVs containing historical records. We have also generated sets of subject-verb-object data as a result of running the routines on portions of the datasets, which are now ready to link in a knowledge graph.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/entity-relationship-extraction>

14. Keeping a Worsted Engineering Expert honest (using Retrieval Augmented Generation) – Asa Calow, Alex Butterworth

Aim: To explore how nineteenth and early twentieth century text resources might be tractable to nascent AI/Machine Learning approaches for the *confident* identification of entities and concepts related to the core ontological concerns of the Textile stand of the project: machinery, processes, activities, occupations.

Conduct: The investigation undertook primary work in the use of the then highly novel Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) technology in the spring of 2023 to explore how the method might be employed to constrain a generative AI to specific historical source material, with initial focus on a technical engineering text about the manufacturing techniques for worsted production ('Woollen and Worsted'), published by Roberts Beaumont in many editions from 1915.³⁷ Multiple iterations refined a process.

Results: Valuable technical insights were derived that predicted/provided reference for the later 'Circulars' investigation (15). The investigation demonstrated the potential for linkage between terms that occur in object metadata (and indeed catalogue data for other heritage types) and sources contemporary with them. Via linked open data this could reduce the need for expert cataloguing by automating links to explanatory material and contexts. Possible other developments of this technique include creating a 'talk to the engineer' interface, a graphical interface that would associate the text both with the intricate illustrations of the source text and machinery and parts held in museum collections, and expansion to other sources (as latterly interrogated through the 'Entity Relation Extraction' investigation, 13). A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

15. Creating a Searchable Database of General Post Office Circulars – Natasha Kitcher, Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi

Aim: Make 100 years of GPO newsletters easier to search for the BT Archive team, taking them beyond a keyword search.

Conduct: We created a RAG pipeline of 10 years of the circulars as a proof of concept. The code we have written is available for other sources to be fed into. The OCR portion of the pipeline relied on LlamaParse while the reasoning is a GPT model, which we have tested against a Custom GPT created earlier in the investigation to see how the RAG pipeline limits hallucination.

Results: This technique shows promise for improving engagement with historical sources, but also risks sacrificing accuracy which we cannot afford to do. Hallucination is limited in the RAG pipeline, but not entirely absent – even in the OCR stage where some unclear text was translated into historical falsehoods.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/retrieval-augmented-generation-with-circulars>

16. Subtitling and summarising of factual video content using Large Language Models –

James Elder

Aim: To see if Large Language Models can help create a speedy workflow to, first, produce faithful transcripts and subtitles of factual films from the BT Group Archives collection; and, second, to summarise the transcripts to provide descriptions suitable for inclusion in the archive catalogue.

Conduct: I first experimented with using OpenAI's voice-recognition and transcription tool Whisper, coupled with Subtitle Edit, to produce subtitles and transcripts. In collaboration with a colleague from BT's AI and Data Science team, I then used Large Language Models (Llama 2 and Zephyr 7B) to produce summaries of the transcripts.

Results: The subtitles and transcripts produced by Whisper were of extremely high accuracy and required only light correction. Approaching 1,000 films have now been subtitled. The summarisation method is only appropriate for films with one or two speakers and a clear narrative voice, but within these restrictions the summaries produced by Zephyr 7B have been useable with little or no amendment. Many are now on the BT Group Archives catalogue - with a note explaining their method of creation. Both methods are in ongoing usage.

Geospatial Linkage

17. Mapping power stations – *Daniel Belteki, Graeme Gooday, Kylea Little, Bernard Musesengwe*

Aims: to examine the history of power stations through digital datasets, with a specific focus on the take-up of Parsons turbo alternators. To examine the connectivity of already available datasets and to identify non-digitised datasets that can aid connectivity.

Conduct: We carried out a transcription of the index to the Parsons & Co. Machine Order Book held at the Tyne & Wear Archives and developed a pipeline to geospatially visualise their delivery destinations using Kepler and Felt mapping apps. These results were subsequently co-visualised with other datasets, including: Historic England (Listed Buildings and Scheduled Monuments), Historic Environment Records (entries matching FISH terms related to energy production), Wikidata (entries for UK power stations), Grace's Guide

(entries for UK power stations), British Electricity History and demographic and socio-economic data for Registration Sub-Districts of England and Wales, 1851-1911.

Results: The investigation produced various mapping visualisations showcasing the complementary nature of historical datasets. A chapter in Emergent Histories describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/mapping-power-stations>

18. The Space Syntax of Worstedopolis – Yichang Sun, Alex Butterworth, Sam Griffith, Daniel Belteki

Aim: To develop a novel conceptual framework for non-geospatial ‘zoomable’ linkage of place and activity through the elaboration and expansion of space syntax principles of micro-geography applied across multiple scales of historical human activity.

Conduct: The investigation explored the transformation of Bradford in the nineteenth century, focusing on the city as a dynamic socio-spatial process within a limited temporal period. By analysing Trade Directory data in time-series (c. 1830, 1842, 1857, 1860, 1887) and applying space syntax as a formal method of spatial-temporal description at the street scale, we link the shape of inhabited space in Bradford to socio-economic data about the textile industry.

Result: The work profiled the fine-grain urban embedding of diverse occupational groups to explore the role of the street network as an emergent source of socio-economic organization that is distinct from other locational factors such as water and transport infrastructure, focusing instead on the role of Bradford textile mills as loci for industrial production. It indicated the value of a space syntax as a foundational framework for the meaningful association of historical data across geographical scale, and at a further remove as a mechanism for associating relevant records and artefacts. A chapter in Emergent Histories describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/microgeographies-of-Worstedopolis>

19. Methods of Spatial Data Linkage – Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi, Daniel Belteki, Matt Bristow (HE), Simon Crutchley (HE), Alex Butterworth

Aim: To develop a disambiguation strategy for mill sites appearing across three Historic England (HE) datasets (Listed Buildings, Records and the Gazetteer).

Conduct: The strategy, developed in collaboration with Historic England, was two-phase and consisted of spatial disambiguation followed by string matching. The spatial disambiguation phase broadly involved creating a series of carefully specified buffers around buildings appearing in HE datasets that could then be used for disambiguation by overlaying the grid references of sites onto the map of buffers. Any grid references falling within a buffer region could then be considered duplicates of the point around which the buffer was originally drawn. Applying this process sequentially to the listed buildings, Historic Environment Record and Gazetteer datasets would eventually leave a residual dataset containing grid references that didn't fall within the perimeters of any of the buffers drawn in the spatial disambiguation process. These residual points would then be disambiguated through a combination of text fuzzy matching and grid reference matching to a specified number of digits.

Results: A well-specified process for disambiguating HE mill sites that is also generalisable and could be extended to other HE sites. The process is now ready to be tested with HE datasets and improved, for example through automating sections.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/methodology-for-spatial-data-linkage>

Time-Based and Audio-Visual Media/Archive

20. Visualising Oral History – *Stefania Zardini Lacedelli, Stef De Sabbata, Alex Butterworth*

Aims: This investigation explored how recent advancements in Large Language Models (LLMs), speech-to-text and visual analytics can provide an innovative way to access and explore oral history archives, enabling their connections with heritage collections and other historical sources.

Conduct: In a preliminary and exploratory study, NER methods and digital curatorial platforms - Omeka and Yarn - were tested to extract and visualize the connections enclosed in a life story. The investigation team then developed a pipeline – which was first applied to a mining dataset from the East Midlands Oral History Archive - comprising three major transformations of the audio material: Speech to Text: in the first phase, Open AI's Whisper was used to transform the audio recordings into textual form tractable to natural language processing methods. Text to vectors: in the second phase, topic modelling tools (LLM-based) were employed to identify broad topics within the interviews by clustering together sentences with similar meaning. Vectors to Insights: in the third phase, the Plotly and Dash python libraries were used to create an interactive dashboard that would provide insights into the whole collection.

Results: The insights, visualisations and interfaces developed in the investigation have shown how responsible use of speech-to-text, Large Language Models (LLMs) and visual analytics can introduce new possibilities for the use of oral histories in museums and historical research. In particular, the investigation developed: Two digital narratives offering an interactive exploration of a life story from the Saltaire Collection; and a proof-of-concept interactive dashboard which allows users to explore a web of automatic-generated topics from the Mines of Memory dataset and visualise the connections of specific sections of the interviews with museum objects from the Snibston Museum. A chapter in Emergent Histories describes the investigation.

<https://congruence-engine.github.io/visualizing-oral-history/>

21. Connecting Industrial Folk Songs with mining and textile collections – *Stefania Zardini Lacedelli, Daniel Belteki, Jennifer Reid, Kunika Kono, Kaspar Beelen*

Aim: This investigation explored how we can use annotation tools to identify connective tissues to link Industrial folk songs to mining and textile collections and integrate the expert knowledge of folk song communities into the linkages.

Conduct: Starting with OCR-generated transcriptions of two industrial folk song anthologies, the investigation team worked with the folk song expert Jennifer Reid to annotate a collection of textile and mining songs, capturing her knowledge through video conversations and textual annotations. In the final phase of the investigation, the research team undertook a preliminary experimental set-up for using the Label Studio annotation platform.

Results: The list of industrial terms and knowledge extracted from the investigation demonstrated the potential for such sources to enrich collection interpretation as well as ontology research in the field of industrial history. Despite showing the potential of text-based annotation tools, the investigation highlighted the need to embed audio-visual methods in the annotation process, to preserve the immediacy of the knowledge exchange and engage with the sonic nature of this material. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://congruence-engine.github.io/connecting-industrial-folk-songs/>

22. Mining Review – *Daniel Belteki, Tim Boon, Stephen McConnachie, Patrick Russell*

Aims: The investigation aimed to assess how we can incorporate contextual information and metadata into the application of multi-modal large language models to the identification and classification of objects on film, and for the creation of detail-rich metadata for individual shots and stills.

Conduct: The investigation incorporated a variety of sources held by the BFI, such as its catalogue metadata, Screenonline descriptions of episodes, digital files of the films, texts written by curators, and archival materials (digitised as part of the investigation). The investigation also tested the potential of ffmpeg and pyScenedetect to automatically identify shot changes for the easier extraction of key scenes from the films. In addition, it tested both LLaVA and Gemini multimodal language models to understand the how contextual information and metadata can be incorporated into prompts.

Results: Digitisation of BFI archival materials related to the production of three Mining Review episodes, 2) Audio transcriptions of digitised Mining Review episodes with Whisper (by OpenAI), 3) Named Entity Recognition analysis (with spaCy) of audio transcriptions, 4) collaborative prompt-writing workshops, 5) prompts designed for Gemini for breaking down digitised films into visual components for metadata integration, 6) Visual outputs of shot boundary detection tools (ffmpeg and PySceneDetect). A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://congruence-engine.github.io/mining-review/>

Digital Infrastructure

23. Occupations Ontology – *Sarah Middle, Alex Butterworth, Arran Rees*

Aim: To design and develop an ontology to describe occupations as activities whose description is time-specific, involving entities that include roles, activities, materials, location of work, etc. Intended as a fulcrum for linkage of diverse entity types, with reference to a set of exemplary sources, with the intention that this should become a core element of the project's data resources. Conceived as a departure from older classificatory systems for defining occupations, this investigation has potential for more dynamic application and use for purposes of, for example, validation of entity extraction using GPT methods.

Conduct: The ontology was developed in rolling consultation between key team members, moving between the specificity of requirements suggested by contemporary resources that were referenced and from which graphable entity-relations data was extracted, and the requirement for conceptual abstraction, with a view to interoperability with other formalised and standardised data resources.

Results: A prototype occupations ontology has been created and is available for adoption and development, focused at this stage on and around the late-nineteenth/early-twentieth century textile industry. A chapter in Emergent Histories describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/industrial-occupations-ontology>

24. Congruence Engine Data Register – Felix Needham Simpson, Kunika Kono, Jane Winters

Aim: To design and develop an online data register resource to provide easily accessible and interpretable information about selected datasets available for research and relevant to specified areas of research interest.

Result: An open-source Registry has been created as a proof-of-concept and demonstrated and tested.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/data-register-app>

25. A Neo4j Graph Database of Household Genealogies (Saltaire 2) – Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi, Alex Butterworth

Aim: To construct a graph of the information extracted from the census by a local historian (28, below), to which data science techniques (e.g. community detection, centrality, path finding) could be applied for the purposes of investigating how individuals listed in the census records were related, not only in terms of family structures but also through their occupations, the tools and materials with which they worked, the physical proximity of their living addresses, their birthplaces etc.

Conduct: To construct the graph, we used a cloud-based instance of Neo4j linked to data stored in secure data storage buckets in the cloud via graph construction routines written in Cypher and Python. Work on exploring the graph is still underway and uses Neo4j's Graph Data Science library, again via routines written in Cypher and Python.

Results: A graph representation of the social network of Saltaire residents between 1861 and 1911, supplemented with extensive information on occupations. The graph model could be further augmented should additional, relevant information become available at a later date. Ongoing data science work will deliver insights into data linkages and clustering in the dataset. A chapter in Emergent Histories describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/census-data-as-a-graph>

26. Developing a Congruence Engine Data Model for Industrial Bradford (Neo4j/Arches) – Jo Kent

Aim: to discover how a great diversity of Bradford social historical data sets might be brought into a cohesive whole as an example of how Congruence Engine could feed into a plan for UK collections linkage

Conduct: Initially the investigation took in a sample of the data to identify the key entities within the domain, such as people, companies, documents and machines. The properties of these, and any additional data held in the datasets, was then modelled and the relationships between them identified. The model was created in the form of a diagram, then recreated and populated with a sample set of the data both as a knowledge graph in Neo4j and within Arches, an open-source data management platform developed for the heritage sector. This

has provided a good basis for further population of the graph and the Arches model which is available to be used for further investigations or for exploration by the wider public.

Result: Proof of concept of the use of Arches for long term data storage. This investigation is the subject of a project blog.³⁸

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/census-data-as-a-graph>

27. Exploring and Increasing Usability of the Arches Data Management System – Alex Butterworth, Jo Kent, Flax&Teal team (Shauna Fitzsimmons, Andrea Kyurchiev, Stuart Marshall, Kanika Miglani, Phil Weir)

A two-phase project, working with Flax&Teal, specialists in the Arches data management system, whose original development was funded by the Getty Resource Institute and used for the Art & Architecture Thesaurus. It is being used and developed by Historic England and advocated for Historic Environment Records.

Aim: To explore the likely requirements for an open-source tool such as this to be amenable for use as part of a localised, federated infrastructure, both for legibility, usefulness and accessibility of reports and for the manual updating of data which is modelled with nuance and complexity.

Conduct: Involved experiments into the development of an improved user interface, including for manual data entry, and of a plug-in to reduce the threshold of expertise and make data upload/integration less painful for non-specialists by identifying points of failure and reasons for obstacles in the data. This was considered in dialogue with HE specialists, other users, its US developer, Getty sponsor, and others. A further phase of research involved identifying obstacles to adoption around ‘silent failure’ on upload and the development of a plug-in for live reporting to obviate this risk.

Results: We have developed solutions to the issues identified, with potential for long-term legacy benefits to a growing community of users, with the aim that this should encourage adoption by academic history and cultural heritage research projects (away from the original archaeology base) in order to nurture interoperability of datasets across disciplinary boundaries. Code will be shared on Github or integrated to core Arches codebase, where possible.

<https://congruence-engine.github.io/arches-usability>

Social Machine I: Human Communities

28. Saltaire Migration and Habitation, An Exercise in Walking Alongside – Alex Butterworth, Colin Coates, Felix Needham Simpson, Duncan Hay

Aim: In the summer of the first year of the project, a workshop was convened to develop collaborative relationships with historians of all kinds, based on the concept of ‘walking alongside’: to understand needs, interests and opportunities and to test the possibilities and challenges involved in building on these. The primary focus was with Colin Coates, a prominent member of the vibrant Saltaire History Club, who is now resident in Australia.

Conduct: Following conversations, access was provided to some of the data gathered and created by Mr Coates about the residents of the town in the nineteenth century. Initial probes into the data considered

multiple possibilities for its use, experimented practicality with mapping migrations into Saltaire, and developed initial design for a programme of genealogical data extraction from census data and its remodelling.

Results: The practical outputs of the project took the form of map-based insights into the local and national distribution of migration into Saltaire, with hypothesis about likely textile expertise being acquired. More significantly, the work demonstrated the value of data-focussed research and contributed to the project's 'digital turn', later that year. The collaboration was significantly illuminating about the value of the extraordinary data resources created and held by independent researchers, the appetite of such researchers for genuine collaboration and technical training, and the potential and challenges of online collaboration, with the additional difficulties of time-zone differences.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/saltaire-migration-habitation>

29. Bradford Convergence – Alex Fitzpatrick, Julia Ankenbrand, Max Long, Natasha Kitcher, Daniel Belteki

Aim: to trial what could be learned by enacting a social machine approach to digitally linked collections in the industrial heritage context of Bradford.

Conduct: Six in-person workshops were developed, each centred around one of the project investigations with connection to Bradford. Each workshop brought together project staff, existing Bradford-based partners and other local heritage practitioners interested in the themes and practices explored in the workshops. The events provided opportunity for a coming together of a wide variety of interests and perspectives on questions like what technical and social relationships and set-ups might be required to sustain an anti-oppressive, distributed practice of digitally linking collections, or what the different motivations might be to be involved in such a process.

Results: Proof of concept and insights into the enrolment of community groups in data creation was achieved. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://github.com.mcas.ms/congruence-engine/bradford-convergence>

30. Zooniverse and Industrial Photographs – Alex Fitzpatrick

Aim: Using online crowdsourcing techniques, this investigation sought to explore motivations for digital engagement with collections, the potential for social infrastructures within the social machine, and how crowdsourced data can be utilised by collection holders.

Conduct: A Zooniverse crowdsourcing project was developed to enable volunteers to transcribe, describe, and identify objects in photographs sourced from Tim Smith's photographic archive and the National Science Media Museum collection relating to the Baird TV factory in Bradford. Overwhelming enthusiasm from hundreds of online volunteers resulted in the project being completed within two days. While the short lifespan meant that there was very little time to capture social activity stemming from the project, comments and responses from volunteers have enabled a glimpse into their motivations, as well as provided a wealth of new data for use by the original collection holders.

Result: Transcription and description tasks completed, and insights into human-sourcing of data (as opposed to generative AI techniques) was achieved. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/zoouniverse-industrial-photographs>

Social Machine II: Interfaces

31. Reanimating the Past Investigation 1 - NERF: Historic England Mill Interiors – Sara Romiti, Alex Butterworth, Ivor Simpson, Alex Appleton

Aim: The rapid advances in Machine Learning capability during the early part of the project, and continuing, suggested a future possibility for regenerating 3D historical spaces from limited still images or moving image frames using Neural Radiance Field technology (NERF), whilst reflecting on how the inevitable partiality of this historical record could be represented visually. The work was intended, in part, to produce material for inclusion in an end of year two digital/interactive exhibit and was expedited for this purpose.

Conduct: Fortuitously, an opportunity presented itself to work with a recent PhD student from the University of Sussex, in collaboration with her supervisor, to test the viability of this technology. Parallel strands of work were undertaken, including an analysis of the number, nature and quality of photographic images required to produce interesting and legible results, and the challenges of identifying historical images of single locations of the required type and number, and documenting these in a form which was useful for assessing their suitability for linkage (across multiple sources) for such a purpose, speculatively.

Results: We started by testing the NERF approach; we analysed evidence of the number of images required to produce acceptable levels of reconstruction but these proved to be higher than expected, and that is likely to be prohibitive when drawing on historical image collections. Ultimately the Gaussian Splatting technique, implemented using specially-shot footage, proved more effective. The accompanying work made progress towards the definition of terms for describing space in historical interior images (with the intention of enabling linkage by reference to a Data Register/Resource Index). Even during the research, it became apparent that the rate of technological development in this area would soon render the results obsolete, as was apparent in the very different potential of zero/few-shot learning for 3D generation in the second stage of this work, a year later. A [blogpost](#) and [film](#) report this work.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/neural-radiance-field-imaging>

32. Reanimating the Past Investigation 2 - Reconstructing Dalton Mills, Keighley in Virtual Reality – Simon Pople, Alex Butterworth, Alex Neish, Yuan Gao and Gyanateet Dutta

Aim: To explore innovative computer vision and generative AI techniques to reconstruct Dalton Mills in Keighley for a VR experience.

Conduct: Because the mill had been damaged by an arson attack, we had to work with limited archival data. To overcome this, we experimented with techniques including PERC for 3D scene generation from panoramas, DUST3R, MAST3R, Spann3r and Splatt3r for reconstructing from uncalibrated images, and Instant Mesh for 3D asset generation from a single image. We also integrated Tencent's Coqui XTTS for voice synthesis, enriching the historical atmosphere of the VR environment. Additionally, we scanned a Holdsworth moquette loom from the Calderdale Industrial Museum with photogrammetry, adding interactive historical objects to the experience. The results were incorporated into Unreal Engine, where we implemented hand tracking and addressed challenges with user locomotion and interaction. The focus was on developing immersive and

interactive contexts in which collections and collections data could be unified and explored using new approaches and High-Performance Computing (HPC) to train and run large AI models.

Results: VR is an excellent archival tool for preserving cultural heritage digitally that can: offer an intimate way to view reconstructed objects; link and unify collections (video, schematics); virtually transport otherwise immovable collections across the world; enable visitor interaction with objects and address accessibility issues around mobility and auditory impairments (hand tracking, immersive and scalable sound design); new 3D reconstruction techniques soon replace photogrammetry for quick scene and object reconstruction; upskilling urgently needed across the sector.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/aesthetics-of-ai-reconstruction>

33. Genealogies and Households Graphical Data Explorer – *Andrew Richardson, Alex Butterworth, Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi*

Aim: To enable users to view and explore household family structures over time, showing both the stories (life-lines) of the individual members of each household (age, status, job etc) over time, and overall change in the composition of each household structure (size, head, family and non-family membership), and the connections between them.

Conduct: A key challenge was to make all of these layers of detail of the composition and relationships of households, and details of the individuals within them, viewable and explorable within an information-dense, interactive and explorable layout.

Results: The final prototype, developed from the core concept, is an information-rich and flexible visualisation that offers an important ‘way in’ for identifying data, enabling users to quickly view and compare characteristics and compositions of household units, individual stories and lifelines. Household characteristics, (complexity, lineage, size, and mortality rate) are revealed through visual properties of circle size, ring number and type, and the number and positioning of nodes. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://congruence-engine.github.io/genealogies-households-explorer>

34. Time-based media Visual Data Explorer – *Andrew Richardson, Alex Butterworth, Stefania Zardini Lacedelli, Stef De Sabbata*

Aim: To explore what forms of visual analysis are required to support a range of expert and non-expert users in the exploration of oral history material in relation to its transcription, the semantic annotation of its content, its non-discourse elements, its provenance and its material contexts.

Conduct: Initially conceived for BFI documentary films and developed during Phase 3 of the oral histories investigation. The work involved the iterative design and development of a user interface to visualise data relevant to the oral histories, with various annotations and metadata accessible and variously visualised at different scales of granularity: collection, interview, speech act/exchange, sentence/segment.

Results: An enhanced exploratory data visualisation interface which allows the user to select, filter and view topics and entities from the Bradford Heritage Recording Unit oral history archive created from a combination of topic modelling and manual annotations via OpenRefine. Further additions are the ability to play the original audio sources and the opportunity to move between different levels of granularity, getting a sense of the paralinguistic

elements of the conversation. The interface is additionally intended to support user-generated curation and annotation. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://congruence-engine.github.io/data-vis-explorer/>

35. Congruent Data Explorer: Phases 1 & 2 – Jack Pay, Alex Butterworth (Phase 1 also: Daniel Belteki, Natasha Kitcher)

Introductory (Phase One): The aim was to explore the use of topic modelling methods for the linkage of collections descriptions. Phase One entailed experimentation in topic modelling across two pairs of distinct (but superficially consonant) museum collection datasets concurrently, and the manual analysis of taxonomically structured annotations during the labelling process. This revealed challenges around the compatibility of the datasets, despite their shared science/industry focus, which pointed to the need for preparatory work on descriptions texts to create more consistent and homogenous subsets that would be more effectively tractable to such a topic modelling approach.

Aim (Phase Two): Phase Two involved the design and development of an open source tool suitable for use by lay users - complementary to an existing topic modelling tool created by the Text Analysis Group at the University of Sussex - which could enable the concurrent exploration of multiple sets of collections metadata to develop subsets, including access to a range of Natural Language Processing methods, towards the creation of embeddings that can be used directly for topic modelling.

Conduct (Phase Two): The project was conducted through an iterative process of design and development, enabled by use of the Solara framework for developing high-performance web applications: a process which was itself revealing about the possibilities and challenges of ‘rapid’ development of tools for data-intensive purposes.

Result (Phase Two): A proof-of-concept output provides researchers with a variety of manual and automated text annotation and exploration methods for sequential application, giving analysts the ability to discover similarities between records across multiple sets of collection metadata and produce targeted subsets for topic-modelling based linkage.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/congruent-data-explorer>

Environment and History

36. Histories of River Pollution in Bradford – Max Long, Tasha Kitcher, Daniel Belteki

Aim: To investigate the history of river pollution in Bradford, with a view to exploring how to combine historic environmental data with other historical sources to develop new historical perspectives in the field of environmental history.

Conduct: We processed reports created as part of the 1868 Royal Commission on River Pollution, using OCR techniques and LLMs to extract complex structured data about the health of individual watercourses, focussing specifically on the impact of the Bradford textile industry on the city’s beck system. We used historic maps from the National Library of Scotland to trace the changing courses of the becks as well as the locations of millponds, contrasting these with other geospatial datasets. We developed a collaboration with

the local campaign group Friends of Bradford's Becks as well as the Aire Rivers Trust to identify how existing historical data was being used to combat current issues in river pollution, and how this could be enhanced.

Results: We hosted a workshop and a public event as part of the 'Bradford Convergence' in May 2024. We have created detailed datasets regarding river pollution in Bradford, which have been shared in Bradford. These datasets have already been used by the Aire Rivers Trust to identify potential sites of ongoing pollution, thanks to identifying lost watercourses. A chapter in the *Emergent Histories* book discusses our learnings with reference to the 'social machine' with specific reference to environmental campaigning and the use of historical data in this context.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/connecting-environmental-data>

Decolonising Histories

37. African Mines Trade Directory – Daniel Belteki, Bernard Musesengwe

Aim: to examine the extent to which digital tools can aid in low-budget and low-tech digitisation and datafication analogue sources; incorporation of extra-UK colonial era data into the energy investigation.

Conduct: we used as an example an African Mines trade directory from the collections of Discovery Museum. We scanned the section related to Zimbabwe, then used ABBY FineReader to OCR-capture it. With the aid of ChatGPT and bespoke Python scripts the captured text was restructured into a structured dataset.

Results: we created visualisations to 1) identify individuals and companies serving as links between the various mines, and 2) the locations of the headquarters of mines (which, it emerged, were mainly in the UK). We sought the help of online communities to assist with the identification of stories related to the mines, but this yielded little additional information. A chapter in *Emergent Histories* describes the investigation.

<https://congruence-engine.github.io/african-mines-directory/>

38. Quarry Bank, National Trust and the Greg Family – Will Ashworth, Stephanie Zardini, Alex Butterworth, Nina Webb-Bourne, Max Long, Nayomi Kasthuri Arachchi

Aim: The investigation developed from the convergence of two broad aims. The first was to explore how a *Congruence Engine* approach to data linkage might help serve the needs and interests of the National Trust's Quarry Bank, an early cotton mill close to Manchester founded by the Greg family of eighteenth/nineteenth century textile entrepreneurs. The second was to consider how to implicate in such data-focused work the colonial and exploitative associations of the cotton industry and the Greg family, specifically.

Conduct: At the core of the research was Ashworth's analogue work to develop a history of the Greg family's business activities in relation to their various networks of association: involving industrial expertise from Scotland, investment in and benefits from slaveholding plantations in the Caribbean and the associated infrastructure, denominational religious practice, and family relations. One strand of work probed how innovative methods, including a GPT-based Entity Relation Extraction approach, might be applied to automatically transform conventional historical writing into machine readable and modellable form. Others explored possible sources of data that would enhance our historical understanding of the Greg family's businesses in relation to slavery, including discussions with the National Trust and access to review Legacies of British Slavery data.

Results: A graphable dataset of core Greg relationships, involving diverse entity-types, was developed, suitable for future expansion. A key finding was the paucity of top-level collections metadata that could explicitly facilitate the discovery of information related to an industrial family's colonial interests. This indicates that it would be beneficial to enhance catalogue information to provide explicit tags to surface certain salient areas of research. Another was that the 'connective tissue' required for relevant data linkage is not readily accessible; that rather than being apparent in direct relationships, it is likely to require deeper interrogation of sources related to intermediaries: bankers, brokers, etc.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/hidden-histories-of-greg-family>

Social History

39. Saltaire socio-economic mapping – Jo Kent

Aim: to use the Booth-Armstrong classification to test the aspirations for socio-economic cohesion in the Saltaire model village.

Conduct: Saltaire is a model village north of Bradford, created to house the workers in Titus Salt's textile mill. As such, it could be expected to provide a better standard of living, and a greater social cohesion than the unplanned urban sprawl of the overpopulated cities of the industrial revolution. We applied the Booth-Armstrong classification of the social class of a household (based on occupation) to the census data for Saltaire. This provided an overview for each census of the socio-economic variance in the village.

Result: An extraordinary level of cohesion was discovered in comparison to the diversity seen on the original Booth poverty maps. This provided an intriguing insight into the social make-up of the village, and a basis for comparison for further study of the surrounding areas, and contrasts with them. A chapter in Emergent Histories describes the investigation.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/saltaire-socio-economic-mapping>

40. Education and social mobility – Jo Kent

Aim: This investigation sought to examine whether Titus Salt's vision for Saltaire not only to escape the overcrowding, but to provide education of an exemplary standard to the residents of the village.

Conduct: Using scholarship and examination records from the archives and the examination of the social classes of the households of the students prior and subsequent to their education using the Booth-Armstrong classification. Comparisons drawn between the residents of Saltaire within the same birth cohort. Then investigation provided an insight into the lives of the students and their comparative success and a starting point for further investigation.

Result: All of the students in the cohort appeared to benefit from their scholarships and were elevated to a higher class than their peers, and also than their families, showing the clear positive effects of education on their lives. This must be caveated with the fact that it was a small sample set and so we would need to examine a larger one before any firm conclusions could be drawn. That said, it certainly gave a very positive indication, and an interesting insight into the lives of families in Saltaire that had not been examined through this lens before. A chapter in Emergent Histories describes the investigation.

Reflexivity and Advisory

41. Environmental impact investigation – *Natasha Kitcher, Max Long, Anna-Maria Sichani*

Aim: Investigate the project's environmental impact.

Conduct: We firstly searched for tools that would allow us to determine a rough figure for our electrical use and carbon impact, but found that these rarely give a clear figure and do not account for use of tools such as LLMs. Instead, we decided to conduct a qualitative study to see how the project team felt about our environmental impact, and focused on increasing awareness (with two team members attending Carbon Literacy training).

Results: We hosted a workshop to share our findings with the team. While the team were enthusiastic about considering our environmental impact, it was broadly accepted this had not been a project priority. We discussed how we could plan projects differently in the future, but also reflected on the relative 'black box' of large tech companies that make it hard to understand the effect of our own work. This work feeds into a forthcoming case study for the Digital Humanities Climate Coalition.

42. Uncovering Positionality in data-driven/AI cultural heritage pipelines – *Anna-Maria Sichani*

Aims: to explore and develop a framework to uncover and assess positionality as it emerged in a series of data/AI-driven pipelines within the social machine of the *Congruence Engine*.

Conduct: Through a literature review on positionality and existing approaches to bias in ML, I have developed a framework to uncover and assess positionality in AI-driven pipelines based on the concept and practice of card-based documentation and assessment. The framework comprises three different cards <people, data, systems>, corresponding to three components in the pipeline structure/concept. Each card includes a number of processes related to the corresponding component in question.

Results: A report and a template for positionality-aware framework for data/AI-driven pipelines.

<https://github.com/congruence-engine/uncovering-positionality>

43. A toolkit on Generative AI, data protection and intellectual property in digital cultural heritage – Anna-Maria Sichani

Aims: to offer comprehensive and accessible information around issues on Generative AI, data protection and intellectual property in digital cultural heritage.

Conduct: For this toolkit I conducted a desktop review of current legislative frameworks on generative AI in the EU and UK, as well as exploring topics and areas of interest related to AI and generative AI. The toolkit is a work-in-progress, currently hosted at a DHRH github repository.

Results: An openly accessible toolkit with information around Generative AI, data protection and intellectual property in digital cultural heritage.

<https://sas-dhrh.github.io/genai-cch-toolkit/>

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